

Understanding and Advancing Female Adolescent Football
Performance: Validating the HumanTrak Movement Analysis
System and Longitudinally Investigating Maturation Effects in
Female Adolescent Players

Mairead Nicola Slevin

April 2024

A thesis submitted to the University of the West of Scotland in partial
fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Research
(MRes).

Supervisors: Dr Laura Forrest, Dr Stephanie Valentin and
Professor Chris Easton

School of Health and Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Declaration

I confirm i) that while registered as a Masters by Research Candidate at the University of the West of Scotland, I have not been enrolled as a student at any other institution of higher education, ii) that this thesis does not contain any material that has been previously submitted for an academic award, and iii) that this work is solely the result of my own efforts, except where acknowledged.

Mairead Slevin

Acknowledgements

I would like to show my upmost appreciation and gratitude to my lead supervisor, Dr Laura Forrest, for her unwavering support, knowledge and commitment. Without her help and guidance this thesis would not have been possible. Dr Stephanie Valentin, your knowledge, advice and expertise have been instrumental in writing this thesis, I cannot thank you enough. To Professor Chris Easton, Dr UChris Ugbolue and Dr Michael King thank you for your specialised knowledge and assistance, it has allowed me to complete this work to the highest standard possible. Your expertise in this field were invaluable in the development of this study.

To Dr Andrew White and Julia Donnelly, without the support from you both, and Athlete Focused I would not be the practitioner I am today. The support I have received from both of you, and Laura from the beginning on my masters is what has allowed me to undertake this research. The experience and opportunities you have provided me with have allowed me to grow and develop my skills and knowledge within an applied environment.

To my parents, your continued love, support and patience over the last two years are what has gotten me through my masters. Without you both I would not be where I am today and for that I will be forever grateful. Dad, I cannot thank you enough for the hours (and hours) you spent helping proofread my work. Euan, Niamh, Aonghas; for pushing me to become the best version of myself and for always supporting me in everything I do. A special thanks to Benn for putting up with my many (many) hiccups and meltdowns and for always believing in me.

To my friends, your patience and continuous encouragement has never gone unnoticed.

I would like to show my appreciation to all the participants who kindly volunteered their time to participate, this research would not have been possible without your time and efforts.

Finally, Glasgow City; specifically all the players and coaching staff who have gone through the 18s National Performance team. I cannot put into words the pride I have for being privileged enough to be a part of this team for the last two years and to coach such an amazing group of young woman. I will cherish the memories and put into practice everything I have learned from being a part of this team. This master's would not have been possible without the support I received from everyone at Glasgow City. Everything else I have gained from being a part of this team and club was an added bonus and has shaped me into the coach and sports scientists I am.

Abstract

Introduction

Tracking performance metrics in relation to biological maturation (BM) in male football has been widely researched, however, is lacking in female football. To track performance, applied sport scientists rely on specialised equipment. Marker-less camera systems to assess functional movements are becoming increasingly popular, however, there is an absence of information surrounding the validity of the HumanTrak Movement Analysis System.

Purpose

Chapter Three investigated the validity of the HumanTrak Movement Analysis System against the gold standard Vicon Motion Capture System through single- and double-leg squat movements. Chapter Four tracks the longitudinal effects of BM on functional movements and performance metrics in adolescent female football players.

Methods

Chapter Three involved 20 participants (10 male and 10 female; age, 24 ± 3 years, body mass; 72.9 ± 15.8 kg, height; 172.1 ± 9.9 cm) completing an overhead squat (OHS) and single-leg squat (SLS) whilst using the HumanTrak system against the gold standard Vicon motion capture system. Knee flexion values were obtained from OHS and SLS and knee varus/valgus values obtained from SLS. Spearman's correlation coefficients were used to report relationships between the two systems and Bland-Altman plots with 95 % CI to depict levels of agreement for knee angles. Chapter Four involved 95 academy female footballers (age 14 ± 2 years) completing four functional movements (single-leg balance, single-leg squat, overhead squat and forward lunge), a countermovement jump (CMJ), 30 m sprint and 1.4 km maximal aerobic speed (MAS) at baseline, 6 and 9-months. Repeated measures analysis of variance were used to determine changes in performance metrics across the three timepoints, Pearson's coefficients to determine the relationship between maturity offset and performance metrics and Independent t-tests to assess differences between pubertal development and performance metrics.

Results

A significant correlation was found between the two systems for knee flexion during both OHS ($r = 0.843$, $p < 0.001$) and SLS ($r = 0.683$, $p < 0.001$). No significant correlation was reported for knee varus/valgus during SLS ($r = 0.104$, $p = 0.663$). Performance metrics measured over a longitudinal period against BM had no significant effect ($p > 0.05$), however, when assessing each variable at individual timepoints, significant relationships between BM and performance metrics were noted for

single-leg right knee varus/valgus ($r = 0.382$, $p < 0.05$) and CMJ ($r = 0.275$, $p < 0.05$) at timepoint A, 30 m sprint time at all three timepoints (A: $r = -0.628$, $p < 0.001$; B: $r = -0.556$, $p < 0.001$; C: $r = -0.596$, $p < 0.001$) and 1.4km MAS at timepoint C ($r = 0.382$, $p = 0.012$). No significant effects of BM on all other performance metrics at all three timepoints were observed ($p > 0.05$). Post-menarche pubertal development scores were significantly lower at all three timepoints for 30 m sprint (A: $p = 0.013$; B: $p = 0.006$; C: $p = 0.003$). All other performance metrics at all timepoints were not significant ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion

Marker-less cameras can accurately report knee flexion values with varus/valgus values noted as invalid. Performance metrics are affected by BM, with the longitudinal effects of BM being insignificant in this study.

Keywords: Biological maturation; female football players; tracking performance; validation.

Table of Contents

Declaration.....	1
Acknowledgements.....	2
Abstract.....	3
Table of Contents.....	5
List of Figures	8
Table of Tables	9
Table of Equations	9
List of Abbreviations	10
List of Operational Terms.....	11
Chapter 1: Introduction	12
Chapter 2: Literature Review	14
2.1 Growth, Maturation and Development	14
2.1.1 Measurements of Biological Maturation	15
2.1.1.1 Dental Age.....	15
2.1.1.2 Skeletal Age.....	15
2.1.1.3 Peak Height Velocity	15
2.1.1.4 Pubertal Development.....	16
2.1.2 Relevance of Biological Maturation in Sport.	18
2.1.3 Relative Age Effect	19
2.2 Importance of Testing Performance Metrics in Football.....	19
2.2.1 Power Performance	21
2.2.2 Sprint Performance	22
2.2.3 Maximal Aerobic Speed	23
2.2.4 Functional Movement Screening.....	23
2.3 Video Analysis	24
2.3.1 Vicon Motion Capture System	25
2.3.2 HumanTrak Movement Analysis System	26
2.4 Aims and Objectives.....	27
Chapter 3: Validity of HumanTrak Movement Analysis System for lower body functional movements.	29

3.1 Introduction	29
3.2 Methods.....	30
3.2.1 Participants	30
3.2.2 Data Collection.....	30
3.2.3 Data Analysis.....	33
3.2.4 Statistical Analysis.....	33
3.3 Results.....	34
3.4 Discussion.....	38
3.5 Conclusion.....	40
Chapter 4: Tracking of performance variables with respect to maturation status in female academy football players over the course of one soccer season.	41
4.1 Introduction	41
4.2 Methods.....	42
4.2.1 Subjects	42
4.2.2 Design.....	42
4.2.2.1 Countermovement Jump	45
4.2.2.2 30 m Sprint.....	46
4.2.2.3 1.4 km Maximal Aerobic Speed	46
4.2.2.4 Biological Maturation.....	46
4.2.2.4.1 Mirwald Predictive Equation.....	46
4.2.2.4.2 Pubertal Development Scale.....	47
4.2.4 Data Analysis.....	47
4.2.5 Statistical Analysis.....	47
4.3 Results.....	48
4.3.1 Single Leg Knee Valgus.....	50
4.3.2 Countermovement Jump	51
4.3.3 30 m Sprint Time	53
4.3.4 1.4 km Maximal Aerobic Speed	54
4.4 Discussion.....	57
4.5 Conclusion.....	60
Chapter 5: General Discussion	62
5.1 Limitations and Future Recommendations.....	63

5.2 Practical Applications.....	64
5.3 General Conclusion	65
6.0 References	67
7.0 Appendices.....	89
7.1 Informed Consent Form for Chapter 1 Validating HumanTrak Movement Analysis System against Vicon Motion Capture System.....	89
7.2 Informed Participant Assent and Parental Consent Form Aged 8-10 for Chapter 2 Tracking performance metrics over one -soccer season.....	90
7.3 Informed Participant Assent and Parental Consent Form Aged 11-15 for Chapter 2 Tracking performance metrics over one -soccer season.....	92
7.4 Informed Participant Consent Form Aged 16+ for Chapter 2 Tracking performance metrics over one -soccer season.	94
7.5 Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire	95
7.6 Self-Report Puberal Development Scale	98
7.7 Chapter 3 Vicon Overhead Squat Graph Export	100
7.8 Chapter 3 Vicon Single-Leg Squat Graph Export.....	101

List of Figures

Figure 1: Modified Helen Hays marker set-up in an anterior (A), lateral (B) and posterior (C) view. ...	31
Figure 2: Participant completing both an overhead squat (OHS) exercise (A) and a single leg squat (SLS) exercise (B). Knee flexion is obtained in Vicon through the x axis and knee varus/valgus in the y axis.	32
Figure 3: Target Zone on HumanTrak which participant must complete all exercises within.	33
Figure 4: Analysis of agreement between HumanTrak and Vicon using Bland-Altman plots. A: Peak knee flexion during the overhead squat (OHS). B: Peak knee flexion of the dominant limb during the single leg squat (SLS). C: Knee varus (positive) or valgus (negative) value at the greatest point of knee flexion during the single leg squat (SLS). The solid line signifies mean difference (bias) between the two systems and the dashed lines signifies the upper and lower limits of agreement ($\pm 1.96SD$).	36
Figure 5: Relationship between HumanTrak and Vicon using correlation coefficients. A: Peak knee flexion during the overhead squat (OHS). B: Peak knee flexion of the dominant limb during the single leg squat (SLS). C: Knee varus (positive) or valgus (negative) value at the greatest point of knee flexion during the single leg squat (SLS).	37
Figure 6: Schematic of Study and Testing Session Overview with progression of testing for each age range.	43
Figure 7: Relationship between years to- and from-PHV (Y-PHV) and single leg knee valgus (degrees) for both the left and right limbs at timepoint A (A), timepoint B (B) and timepoint C (C).	51
Figure 8: Relationship between years to- and from-PHV (Y-PHV) and countermovement jump (CMJ) height (cm) at timepoint A (A), timepoint B (B) and timepoint C (C).	52
Figure 9: Relationship between years to- and from-PHV (Y-PHV) and 30 m sprint time (seconds) at timepoint A (A), timepoint B (B) and timepoint C (C).	53
Figure 10: Relationship between years to- and from-PHV (Y-PHV) and 1.4 km maximal aerobic speed (MAS) (m/s) at timepoint A (A), timepoint B (B) and timepoint C (C).	55

Table of Tables

Table 1: Participant characteristics (N = 20) and knee flexion and varus/valgus angles for HumanTrak and Vicon for overhead squat (OHS) and single-leg squat (SLS).....	34
Table 2: Comparative results of knee flexion and varus/valgus obtained from HumanTrak and Vicon systems during overhead (OHS) and single-leg (SLS) squats.	35
Table 3: Average outdoor temperature in degrees Celsius (reported as a mean and standard deviation) for each age group at timepoint A (baseline), timepoint B (6-months) and timepoint C (9-months). 44	
Table 4: Maturity offset and performance metrics for all three testing timepoints. Timepoint (TP) A is baseline, Timepoint (TP) B is six months from baseline and timepoint (TP) C is nine months from baseline. Statistical significance was set at $p = 0.05$	49
Table 5: Comparison of pre-menarche and post-menarche participants for all performance metrics at all three timepoints (mean \pm SD). Analysis is based on a split of pubertal development, with participants not yet reached menarche; pre-menarche (P2-P3) and participants having started menstruation; post-menarche (P4-P5). Statistical Significance noted where $p < 0.05$	56

Table of Equations

Equation 1: Mirwald Predictive Equation for females.....	46
Equation 2: Leg Length Calculation.	46
Equation 3: Peak Height Velocity (PHV) Calculation.	47

List of Abbreviations

BM	Biological maturation
MO	Maturity offset
PHV	Peak height velocity
Y-PHV	Years to- or from- peak height velocity
RAE	Relative age effect
RA	Relative age
FMS	Functional Movement Screen
PDS	Pubertal Development Scale
CMJ	Countermovement jump
OHS	Overhead squat
SL	Single leg
SLS	Single leg squat
MAS	Maximal aerobic speed
3D	Three-dimensional
ASIS	Anterior superior iliac spine
LoA	Limits of agreement
ICC	Intraclass correlation coefficient
CI	Confidence intervals

List of Operational Terms

Biological Maturation: The process during adolescences where all tissues, organs and systems in the body develop to a mature state.

Peak Height Velocity: Describes the period of most rapid growth in height during adolescence.

Overhead squat: An athlete stands with feet shoulder width apart and toes slightly and comfortable turned out. The athlete then squats as low as possible towards the ground while holding a lightweight pole with straight arms above the crown of their head.

Single leg squat: An athlete performs a squatting movement on one leg trying to get as much depth as possible. The athlete will have their arms crossed over their shoulders, their knee and hip at 90 degrees flexion and their heel remaining on the ground.

Countermovement jump: A vertical jump where an athlete performs a quick squat then immediately jumps as high as possible. Jump height is recorded in centimetres.

30 m sprint: Running at maximal speed over a thirty meters distance through timing gates, starting from a stationary position 1 meter behind the first timing gate. Sprint time is recorded in seconds.

1.4 km Maximal Aerobic Speed: Running a set distance of 1.4 km in a short a time as possible. Maximal aerobic speed is recorded in meters per second (m/s).

Validity: How accurate a method, technique or system is at measuring what it is intended to, usually compared against a 'gold standard' method of measurement.

Chapter 1: Introduction

The evolution of sporting analysis has accelerated since the digital age, with constant improvements and advancements in technology (Luo, Gao and Wang, 2021; Pino-Ortega *et al.*, 2022a). Technological developments have allowed researchers and practitioners to formulate more educated decision-making throughout training and competition from both a physical and technical perspective (Windt *et al.*, 2020). Technology is now used by sport professionals in training and competition to enhance performance (Yuliandra, Nugroho and Gumantan, 2020; McCosker *et al.*, 2022). Most sports use technological systems such as goal-line technology (Halder, Saha and Shaw, 2023), injury screening and prevention systems (Claudino *et al.*, 2019), global positioning systems (GPS) and video analysis for the evaluation of training load, tactical analysis and performance (Zhang, 2022). The improvement in monitoring technologies allows collection and analysis of data which is key for the development of physical performance (Luo, Gao and Wang, 2021) and supports a better understanding of the physical demands required to excel in any sport (Li and Xu, 2021). Tracking performance data through technologies also facilitates the ability to plan and monitor external load, to determine competition readiness and to minimise risk of injury for athletes (Torres-Ronda *et al.*, 2022). Specifically, vision-based systems were in use as early as the late nineteenth century for simplistic gait analysis through photographic based image capture (Colyer *et al.*, 2018). The advent of motion analysis led to the development of marker and marker-less systems to track multiple movements within sporting performance (Colyer *et al.*, 2018). Any new technology monitoring system requires validation prior to adoption from sporting professionals and bodies. Football is a key stakeholder in the validation and adoption of motion analysis technologies and football associations have been at the forefront of using goal-line technology (Ajjampur, Shridhar and Shashikala, 2021; Kırkoğlu, 2023; Păun, 2023), GPS systems (Malone *et al.*, 2017; Schulze, Julian and Skorski, 2021; Guitart *et al.*, 2022) and sprint timing gates (Vescovi and Jovanović, 2021; Zabaloy *et al.*, 2024).

Football is one of the most popular sports in the world. It is a highly dynamic sport with unpredictable changes throughout a 90-minute match and has a large number of players to track (Rajšp and Fister, 2020; Tuyls *et al.*, 2021). In recent years, the growth of women's football has increased exponentially and, consequently, professional and youth participation has also risen (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Mainer-Pardos *et al.*, 2021; Randell *et al.*, 2021). This has led to improvements in the support the women's game receives through the media, financial backing and sports science and medical support (Scelles, 2021; Okholm Kryger *et al.*, 2022). The latter has led to a growing interest in player wellbeing and development and, specifically, the impact growth and maturation has on adolescent's performance (Griffin *et al.*, 2021). Growth and maturation is a period of continuous change and development throughout childhood and adolescence which every individual will experience in their own unique

timeframe and can hold a beneficial or detrimental impact on sporting performance (Malina *et al.*, 2015a; Fransen, Skorski and Baxter-Jones, 2021). Currently, the majority of research conducted on growth and maturation in football is within male academy settings (Philippaerts *et al.*, 2006; Lloyd *et al.*, 2015; Asadi *et al.*, 2018; Eskandarifard *et al.*, 2022; King *et al.*, 2022a) and suggests increased maturation has a positive impact on performance metrics of speed, power and strength (Philippaerts *et al.*, 2006; Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2011; Lloyd *et al.*, 2015; Peña-González *et al.*, 2018; Parr, Winwood, Hodson-Tole, Deconinck, Parry, *et al.*, 2020; Radnor *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, with the rapid uptake of women's football and limited understanding in female academies, there is a need to further understand growth and maturation of female athletes to aid and advance youth football due to the rates at which maturation occurs is different between males and females (Datson *et al.*, 2020).

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Growth, Maturation and Development

Growth, maturation and development are the terms used to describe three of the physical and physiological processes children and young people experience for approximately the first 20 years of their lives (Baxter-Jones, Thompson and Malina, 2002; Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004). Growth is characterised by the increase in size of an individual's body through childhood and adolescence, for example, as children grow, they become taller and heavier due to the increase in bone length, organ size and muscle mass (Baxter-Jones, Thompson and Malina, 2002; Chandrasekar *et al.*, 2020). Maturation is defined as the process towards reaching an "adult state", when an individual's physiological systems undergo periods of growth and change (Parr, Winwood, Hodson-Tole, Deconinck, Hill, *et al.*, 2020; Peña-González *et al.*, 2022). Maturation is split into two categories: timing and tempo. Timing, outlined as the timepoints at which events of maturation occur, for example the age which breast development starts in females (Parr, Winwood, Hodson-Tole, Deconinck, Hill, *et al.*, 2020). Tempo is described as the speed at which these developments occur, for example how quickly breasts develop (Parr, Winwood, Hodson-Tole, Deconinck, Hill, *et al.*, 2020). Development is explained as the learning of cognitive, emotional and social skills within different environments such as at home, in school or through participation in sport (Baxter-Jones, Thompson and Malina, 2002). The impact growth, maturation and development have on sporting performance is currently gaining considerable attention within the scientific community (Armstrong and Mechelen, 2023), in talent identification (Eisenmann, Till and Baker, 2020; Till and Baker, 2020) and by sporting governing bodies and stakeholders (Ryan *et al.*, 2018; Johnson *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, it is essential we understand the effects growth, maturation and development have on the body during sports performance to better support individuals during this transition (Kim and Lim, 2014).

Biological maturation (BM) is the term used to define the progression of all biological systems, tissues and organs to reach a fully mature adult state (Malina *et al.*, 2015a; Towlson *et al.*, 2022). This biological development is said to be one of the most dynamic stages throughout an individual's life, which is very much a non-linear process due to the changes in body composition, stature, the neuroendocrine system, and fertility (Biro *et al.*, 2001; Garcia *et al.*, 2018; Mendle *et al.*, 2019). Maturation is a process every individual undergoes, however, can vary depending on a number of factors including, but not limited to, an individual's genetics, their environment and their ethnicity (Parr, Winwood, Hodson-Tole, Deconinck, Hill, *et al.*, 2020; Towlson *et al.*, 2022). Individuals with the same chronological age can vary as much as five-to-six years in skeletal and biological age (Lloyd *et al.*, 2014; Towlson *et al.*, 2022). In addition, this can further vary between males and females, with females

commonly going through development earlier than their male counterparts (Lloyd and Oliver, 2012a; Albaladejo-Saura *et al.*, 2022).

2.1.1 Measurements of Biological Maturation

Biological maturation can be assessed through multiple methods using a variety of different indicators including dental age, skeletal age, peak height velocity and secondary sexual characteristics also known as pubertal development (Chandrasekar *et al.*, 2020; Goncharuk-Khomyn *et al.*, 2020).

2.1.1.1 Dental Age

Dental age is estimated through permanent tooth formation using radiography, with development varying between populations (De Tobel *et al.*, 2017; Esan, Yengopal and Schepartz, 2017). In adolescents, dental age is evaluated through the third molars as these teeth are still developing (De Tobel *et al.*, 2017). Variation in dental development has been reported between sex with females advancing quicker in tooth formation than their male counterparts (Oziegbe, Esan and Oyedele, 2014; Esan, Yengopal and Schepartz, 2017; Karimi *et al.*, 2021). The most commonly used method for assessing dental age in children is the Demirjian's method (Demirjian, Goldstein and Tanner, 1973). Using radiography imaging, the results categorise every child into one of the eight stages of tooth development (Manzoor Mughal, Hassan and Ahmed, 2014; Sehrawat and Singh, 2017). A modified version of this method was introduced in 2001, the Willems method (Willems *et al.*, 2001), which simplifies the dental age estimations through expressing dental maturity in both sex and age categories (Manzoor Mughal, Hassan and Ahmed, 2014; Sehrawat and Singh, 2017).

2.1.1.2 Skeletal Age

Skeletal age, also known as bone age, assesses maturation through skeletal tissue, mainly at the hand and wrist (radius, ulna, carpals, metacarpals and phalanges) using radiography or ultrasound imaging (Malina, 2011; Lloyd *et al.*, 2014; Malina *et al.*, 2015a; Rüeger *et al.*, 2022). It involves long-term analysis of the bones in both the hand and wrist from early ossification (bone formation) throughout growth and into adult state (Lloyd *et al.*, 2014; Malina *et al.*, 2015a). Ultrasound imaging is used in areas of high bone ossification or where cartilage is present to allow close monitoring of the growth plate and give an estimation of skeletal maturity (Dirksen, 2022; Rüeger *et al.*, 2022). Skeletal age and dental age combined are determined as the most favourable method of assessing biological age (Shi *et al.*, 2018), however, these methods come with limitations due to the time-consuming nature of long-term assessment, the need for specialist equipment and personnel and the overall cost required to determine skeletal or dental age (Lloyd *et al.*, 2014).

2.1.1.3 Peak Height Velocity

Height velocity is defined as the rate at which a child grows and is usually measured in centimetres per year (Cole, 2012). Peak Height Velocity (PHV) is the fastest period of growth, in height, during

adolescence and generally occurs around the age of 12 years for females and 14 years for males (Malina *et al.*, 2004, 2015a; Kozieł and Malina, 2018; Peña-González *et al.*, 2022). It is a somatic estimation of maturation, describing the growth in stature and is the most commonly used method within sport (Mills *et al.*, 2017; Kozieł and Malina, 2018; Peña-González *et al.*, 2022). The age at which PHV occurs can be calculated using the sex specific linear Mirwald equation (Mirwald *et al.*, 2002; Section 4.1.3.4.1; Equation 1) for both males and females using chronological age, body mass, standing height and seated height to assess maturity offset (Lloyd *et al.*, 2014; Malina *et al.*, 2015a; Kozieł and Malina, 2018). Maturity offset is then subtracted from the individual's chronological age to obtain the age at PHV. However, the error in estimation for this method indicates a ± 1 year error for maturity offset in 95 % of calculations and is most applicable in a sample of individuals aged 10 – 18 years (Mirwald *et al.*, 2002; Fransen *et al.*, 2018; Fransen, Skorski and Baxter-Jones, 2021).

The Khamis and Roche Method (Khamis and Roche, 1994) is another technique used to predict PHV. This is a non-invasive linear method utilising an individual's chronological age, height, body mass and mid-parental height (an average of both biological parent's heights) for both males and females (Khamis and Roche, 1994; Fransen, Skorski and Baxter-Jones, 2021). This allows for the individual's current height to be expressed as a percentage of their predicted adult height, allowing maturation to be estimated (Malina *et al.*, 2019). Individuals with the same chronological age, who are closer to adult height, are more mature than individual's further from adult height. This method has errors in estimation for both males (5.3 ± 1.4 cm) and females (4.3 ± 1.6 cm) at 90% error bound (Khamis and Roche, 1994; Fransen, Skorski and Baxter-Jones, 2021) and requires both biological parent's height which may be challenging to obtain.

A recent equation, the Fransen equation (Fransen *et al.*, 2018), is an update of the Mirwald equation to improve the estimated age of PHV for males through a maturity ratio (Fransen *et al.*, 2018; Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). This equation provides a more precise estimation of the non-linear process of maturation (Fransen, Skorski and Baxter-Jones, 2021; Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). However, the equation has a ± 1 year error in estimation (Towlson *et al.*, 2021) and is only available for estimating male PHV with no maturity ratio available for females (O'Brien-Smith *et al.*, 2020; Towlson *et al.*, 2021). Due to the biological differences between males and females, it is expected a separate Fransen equation updated from the Mirwald equation should be introduced to improve PHV estimation for females (Fransen *et al.*, 2018).

2.1.1.4 Pubertal Development

Sexual age, otherwise known as pubertal development, is referred to as the development towards the reproductive systems reaching full function (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004; Lloyd *et al.*, 2014). This involves pubertal growth in accordance with an individual's developmental or biological age

rather than their chronological age (Cole, 2012). Pubertal development is a series of complex biological processes which occur in the body and can be characterised by an individual's ability to reproduce (Brooks-Gunn and Peterson, 2013; Witchel and Topaloglu, 2019). These processes usually starts earlier in females (~11 years old) than in males (~13 years old), with the duration of processes varying for every individual (Rogol, Roemmich and Clark, 2002). For both males and females, an increase in the adrenal androgen hormones produced by the adrenal gland results in the development and appearance of pubic hair, body odour and oily skin (Rogol, Roemmich and Clark, 2002; Spaziani *et al.*, 2021). The gonadal steroid hormones increase the secretion of the sex steroids. In males, this is the production of testosterone which controls functions such as the increase of testicular growth and the production of spermatozoa (commonly known as sperm) (Rogol, Roemmich and Clark, 2002; Witchel and Topaloglu, 2019; Spaziani *et al.*, 2021). Females secrete the sex steroids oestrogen and progesterone which have multiple functions. For example, oestrogen aids the development of an individual's breast development (thelarche) and menarche (first occurrence of menstruation) (Malina *et al.*, 2015a; Mendle *et al.*, 2019; Witchel and Topaloglu, 2019) and progesterone protects the endometrial lining (Di Renzo, Tosto and Tsibizova, 2020) and plays a vital role during pregnancy (Cable and Grider, 2023).

The 'gold standard' or optimal method to assess pubertal development is the Tanner criteria (Tanner, 1962) which involves clinicians examining an individual's body for changes in secondary sexual characteristics (Lloyd *et al.*, 2014; Mendle *et al.*, 2019). However, it is deemed an invasive method which could make adolescents feel uncomfortable during observation, requires parental consent and necessitates a trained medical professional to complete the assessment (Mendle *et al.*, 2019). The Tanner criteria, also known as the Sexual Maturation Scale, assesses pubertal status based on the individual's secondary sexual characteristics and is categorised into five stages (Tanner, 1962; Lloyd *et al.*, 2014; Mendle *et al.*, 2019). Stage one is classed as no visibility of pubertal development, through to stage five suggesting full pubertal development; for example, in females, full growth of pubic hair and breast development (Tanner, 1962; Marshall and Tanner, 1969). This method of assessment can have variabilities in results due to differences between trained clinicians and pubertal development occurring at different timescales with individuals potentially skipping stages (Lloyd *et al.*, 2014).

A non-invasive alternative which is often used as an approach to assessing pubertal development is self-assessments or screening tools (Mendle *et al.*, 2019). This could be an assessment of the Tanner Criteria which entails the individual and/or their parent using photographs or images to assess the stage of pubertal development (Tanner, 1962; Mendle *et al.*, 2019). Yet, this could cause individuals to under- or over report their development (Leone and Comtois, 2007; Mendle *et al.*, 2019). There is variability in the errors of estimation as males tend to overestimate their pubertal development and

females more commonly underestimating their development (Williams *et al.*, 1988; Leone and Comtois, 2007). However, less than 70 % of females accurately self-reported their pubertal development (Wu *et al.*, 2001; Shirtcliff, Dahl and Pollak, 2009) with an overestimation in the earlier stages of pubertal development and under-estimation in the later stages (Bond *et al.*, 2006).

The Carskadon and Acebo (1993) pubertal development scale (PDS) is another self-report, non-invasive method determining pubertal stage of adolescents. Conducted in the form of a questionnaire, with five questions for the individual to answer, it is separated for males and females allowing for sex-specific questions to be answered (Petersen *et al.*, 1988). The questions for each sex assesses perceived changes in; height, body or pubic hair and skin, with deepening of voice and facial hair for males and changes in breast development and menarche (onset of menstruation) in females (Petersen *et al.*, 1988; Carskadon and Acebo, 1993; Mendle *et al.*, 2019). The responses from the questionnaire are weighted, which allows each individual to be categorised; pre-, early-, mid-, late- or post-pubertal (Koopman-Verhoeff *et al.*, 2020). This method is a valid and reliable measure of pubertal development reported to have a high association with the Tanner Sexual Maturation Scale for both males and females (Petersen *et al.*, 1988; Emmanuel and Bokor, 2017; Koopman-Verhoeff *et al.*, 2020).

2.1.2 Relevance of Biological Maturation in Sport.

When comparing youth players within sport, it is important to consider the effects maturation could have on performance and whilst players will have a similar chronological age within an age grouping, their maturity status may vary (Peña-González *et al.*, 2022). Individuals who have more pronounced physical attributes during their adolescent years can be identified with higher skill levels and talent, resulting in later maturing players being overlooked (King *et al.*, 2022b). During biological maturation, athletes undergo prolonged periods of physical change which can have an effect on performance and vary significantly depending on the individual (Guimarães *et al.*, 2021). Substantial alterations to individual's hormonal profiles, body and muscle mass, and muscular coordination (Lloyd *et al.*, 2014) occur during this period of biological maturation which impacts on physiological and physical development (Lloyd *et al.*, 2015). This period can be described as 'adolescent awkwardness' (Towilson *et al.*, 2022). For instance, the increase in limb length and body/muscle mass during biological maturation can cause fluctuations in coordination levels and, therefore, affect performance (Lloyd *et al.*, 2015).

In males, maximal gains in speed, strength, aerobic capacity and agility, are suggested to occur close to PHV (Philippaerts *et al.*, 2006; Valente-dos-Santos *et al.*, 2012), whereas in females, these performance gains are said to plateau around and after PHV (Manna, 2014). Males have an increased level of testosterone around PHV and pubertal development compared to females, therefore males are considered to be stronger and faster than females (Manna, 2014). However, improvement in

performance metrics are said to be greater in players post-PHV when assessing the impact of maturation on male athletes (Asadi *et al.*, 2018; Torres-Ronda *et al.*, 2022). This results in later maturing male athletes being unable to beat earlier maturing opponents as they have less developed speed, strength and aerobic capabilities with an increased risk of injury due to not having fully completed maturation (Manna, 2014).

2.1.3 Relative Age Effect

During the talent selection process in particular team sports, variations in cognition and physical ability can be seen due to an individual's biological age (Brustio *et al.*, 2022). Team sports often split athletes into groups by their chronological age based on the sporting calendar year (Helsen, van Winckel and Williams, 2005). For example, football, or rather Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA), uses chronological age to group players into competition teams usually falling into two-year periods (for example, Under-14, Under-16) (Peña-González *et al.*, 2022; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2023). Across multiple sports, it is believed athletes born at the start of the sporting calendar year have a greater maturity state (Peña-González *et al.*, 2022; Towlson *et al.*, 2022). Therefore these athletes often possess increased anthropometric and performance characteristics (such as speed, endurance, strength) than players born later in the sporting calendar year (Cobley *et al.*, 2009; Reed, Parry and Sandercock, 2017; Peña-González *et al.*, 2022; Towlson *et al.*, 2022). As a result, coaches tend to select relatively older players (by as much as 61%) due to anticipating a higher performance level in order to achieve their desired result of their team winning (Vincent and Glamser, 2006; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2023). This over representation of older players in an age-group team is known as the Relative Age Effect (RAE) and is often present in academy settings (Deprez *et al.*, 2013; Andrew *et al.*, 2022). However, when researching relative age and maturity status, there is small (Peña-González *et al.*, 2022) to no relationship between relative age and maturity status on player's performance metrics (Cumming *et al.*, 2018; Parr, Winwood, Hodson-Tole, Deconinck, Hill, *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, relative age and maturity status should be treated as two separate, individual variables when discussing the effects on youth sporting performance (Parr, Winwood, Hodson-Tole, Deconinck, Hill, *et al.*, 2020; Peña-González *et al.*, 2022).

2.2 Importance of Testing Performance Metrics in Football

Depending on the sport and physical capabilities required, testing and data collection method can vary and should be tailored to the demands of a specific sport (Pyne, Spencer and Mujika, 2013; Poehling *et al.*, 2021). The ability to track and assess human movement during sport is vital for athletic performance, improvement of technique, prevention and rehabilitation of injury, and decision-making and talent identification (Datson *et al.*, 2020; Taborri *et al.*, 2020).

Testing athletes, particularly youth athletes, is deemed important to understand physical characteristics and the impact of these characteristics on performance, allowing coaching staff to support and tailor training for these athletes depending on their stage of growth and maturation (Poehling *et al.*, 2021; Ramos *et al.*, 2021). Field based tests are preferred when determining physical capabilities of athletes as they offer sport-specific alternatives to laboratory-based testing which cannot be conducted in the training/match environment (Julian and Sargent, 2020). Current field-based research has predominantly been conducted at a single time point, however to gain a greater understanding of the impact of maturation on performance metrics, data should be collected over multiple time points (Lloyd *et al.*, 2014; Till *et al.*, 2014; Emmonds *et al.*, 2020).

In males, maturation influences different physical performance attributes including jump height (Asadi *et al.*, 2018; Almeida-Neto *et al.*, 2021; Eskandarifard *et al.*, 2022), sprint speed (Deprez *et al.*, 2013; Gastin, Bennett and Cook, 2013; McCunn *et al.*, 2017), quality of movement and repeated sprint ability (Spencer *et al.*, 2005; King *et al.*, 2022b). There is a growing body of evidence to support the physiological differences between males and females and the different responses and adaptations to exercise (Ansdell *et al.*, 2020; Cowley *et al.*, 2021). These include energy metabolism, muscular strength, lower limb biomechanics and sex hormones (Maggi and Della Torre, 2018; Solomito, Reuman and Wang, 2019; Roberts, Nuckols and Krieger, 2020; Cowley *et al.*, 2021; Herman *et al.*, 2022). For instance, males generally tend to be taller, stronger and faster than females, specifically during and after maturation (Hewett, Myer and Ford, 2004; Capranica *et al.*, 2013; Herman *et al.*, 2022). This is potentially due to the increased production of testosterone being higher in male adolescents (Manna, 2014) and the unique fluctuations in hormone production in females which can lead to a reduced muscular strength during puberty (Sommerfield *et al.*, 2022).

Traditionally, females have been largely excluded from scientific research in sport due to the biological variation of their reproductive system, potential harm to foetuses and historically being considered “fragile” and the “weaker sex” (Capranica *et al.*, 2013; Shields and Lyerly, 2013; Mujika and Taipale, 2019). It was easier to eliminate females and these biological differences or ‘complications’ from research, instead of understanding female physiology functions and the effect on various aspects of exercise and performance. This resulted in females accounting for less than 40 % of original research (Costello, Bieuzen and Bleakley, 2014; Mujika and Taipale, 2019), with currently only 6 % of sport and exercise science literature researching solely women (Cowley *et al.*, 2021), therefore leaving females significantly under-represented in research literature. Additionally, most guidelines and practices in sport and exercise science for female athletes have been previously underpinned by studies using male participants (Emmonds, Heyward and Jones, 2019; Cowley *et al.*, 2021; Elliott-Sale *et al.*, 2021).

Female sports can have differing demands from their male counterparts with lighter equipment, shorter distances, or fewer events (Smith, McKay, Ackerman, *et al.*, 2022; Smith, McKay, Kuikman, *et al.*, 2022). In football, females cover a shorter distance, have ~ 30 % lower high intensity runs and complete fewer sprints compared to their males counterparts during a typical match (Bradley *et al.*, 2014; McFadden *et al.*, 2020; Romero-Moraleda *et al.*, 2021). However, these differences in performance demands could be reflective of the differences in training status or match demands instead of biological differences (Pedersen, Aksdal and Stalsberg, 2019). The training age of male footballers is also, usually, greater than that of female footballers due to male players participating in the sport longer, having started training at a younger age (Rumpf *et al.*, 2014) and due to the masculinity, perceptions and lack of participation of females in football activities within the school playground (Martínez-García and Rodríguez-Menéndez, 2020; Kostas, 2022; Arlinkasari, Cushing and Miller, 2023). Therefore, to adequately understand and inform the effects of maturation on female athletes, data must be recorded and collated on the physical characteristics specifically for female athletes (Torres-Ronda *et al.*, 2022).

It is suggested there is a non-linear increase in performance metrics of speed (Edwards *et al.*, 2021; Ramos *et al.*, 2021), agility, endurance (Hackett *et al.*, 2023) and power (Richter *et al.*, 2010; Haugen, Tønnessen and Seiler, 2012) with relation to BM, especially around PHV (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2023). Reference values have recently been published for performance metrics of power, endurance capacity and speed within women's football to support practitioners and coaches when testing youth females (Datson *et al.*, 2022). These values show an overall gradual improvement of performance metrics until the age of 25 years (Poehling *et al.*, 2021; Datson *et al.*, 2022). However, longitudinal tracking of female performance metrics and maturation within football is limited, with only one study conducting irregular testing of national team players in measurements of speed, power and aerobic fitness over a five year period (Poehling *et al.*, 2021). More research is needed to give females sex-specific guidelines and practices (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Cowley *et al.*, 2021; Okholm Kryger *et al.*, 2022).

2.2.1 Power Performance

Countermovement Jump (CMJ) is a performance test used within multiple sports to assess lower-limb power (Datson *et al.*, 2022). The CMJ is an extensively used, valid and reliable performance test used by practitioners around the world (Heishman *et al.*, 2018; Warr *et al.*, 2020). The standardised method used to measure CMJ involves the participants hands remaining on their hips throughout the jump to eliminate any variation between participants and other research studies which allows for analysis between results (Heishman *et al.*, 2018; Warr *et al.*, 2020). In female footballers, lower-limb power and CMJ height fluctuate around PHV due to the non-linear process around maturation and

development (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020). Measurements of CMJ height, from Under-10 to under-18s, have shown to be greater in older adolescents who are past their period of most rapid growth (Vescovi *et al.*, 2011; Haugen, Tønnessen and Seiler, 2012; Emmonds *et al.*, 2018; Jeras, Bovend'Eerd and McCrum, 2020). This could be a result of a less developed stretch-shortening cycle in younger adolescents due to reduced muscle size, rate of force development or reactive strength index (Castagna and Castellini, 2013; Radnor *et al.*, 2018; Jeras, Bovend'Eerd and McCrum, 2020). Adolescents with a less developed stretch-shortening cycle can have a reduced flight time during their CMJ due to being unable to store and utilise large amounts of elastic energy during the eccentric phase (downward movement) of the jump (Thapa *et al.*, 2024).

Following this period of rapid growth, CMJ height is said to increase gradually until ~25 years old before reaching a plateau and decreasing following this period (Datson *et al.*, 2022), with senior female football players having a ~4 cm increase in CMJ height compared to adolescent female football players (Mujika *et al.*, 2009). As such, practitioners and coaches working with adolescents need awareness of the impact maturation may have on physical characteristics and performance metrics such as CMJ of female football players (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020).

2.2.2 Sprint Performance

Sprint ability is considered to be an appropriate fitness measure within football due to the number of high intensity runs made throughout a match (Chaouachi *et al.*, 2010; Filter *et al.*, 2020). Sprint testing is a valid and reliable tool widely used by practitioners within sports science (Altmann *et al.*, 2019; Pavillon *et al.*, 2021). Participants starting 1 metre behind the first timings gate is a well-used and reliable protocol to measure the sprint performance ensuring participants start from a static position (Krolo *et al.*, 2020), however a rolling-start is another frequently used protocol (Caldbeck and Dos'Santos, 2022; Michailidis, Metaxas and Moutsanos, 2022) and both of these protocols mimic the nature of the sport and are used within the literature (Caldbeck and Dos'Santos, 2022). Various timings gates (for example, Whitty, Brower, VALD) can be used to measure sprint ability and all are established, valid pieces of equipment to use within the field (Brown, Vescovi and VanHeest, 2004; Papla *et al.*, 2020; Pavillon *et al.*, 2021). Women's football players cover on average 8-13 km during a football match, with 0.2-1.7 km covered at high speed (Haugen *et al.*, 2014; Martínez-Lagunas, Niessen and Hartmann, 2014; Vescovi and Favero, 2014). Adolescents sprint ability is considered a non-linear process with improvements occurring at different stages of maturation (Edwards *et al.*, 2021). Testing sprint distance is generally completed over a distance ranging from 5-40 metres (Haugen *et al.*, 2014), with velocity increasing steadily over the time period of 12- to 16 years old (Poehling *et al.*, 2021).

The greatest change in sprint time is often observed between -2.5 and +0.5 PHV (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020) with faster sprint times in distances between 5 and 40 m being quicker in older players who

have reached PHV and who are further through BM (Vescovi *et al.*, 2011; Bradley *et al.*, 2014; Emmonds *et al.*, 2018, 2020; Mainer-Pardos *et al.*, 2021; Ramos *et al.*, 2021). It should also be noted an increase in sprint speed was evident for senior women's players when compared to adolescents (Ramos *et al.*, 2021). Altogether, this could be a result of increased height at puberty, consequently increasing lower limb length, reducing stride length of older adolescents (Schepens, Willems and Cavagna, 1998; Emmonds *et al.*, 2018; Mainer-Pardos *et al.*, 2021).

2.2.3 Maximal Aerobic Speed

Aerobic capacity can be assessed through multiple field-based tests including Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery, Multistage Fitness Test, 1200 metre Shuttle Test and set distance time trials (Baker and Heaney, 2015; Walker, 2016b; Hackett *et al.*, 2023). These tests can estimate maximal aerobic capacity as an alternative to the lab-based protocols using highly specialised equipment (Tabacchi *et al.*, 2019). Maximal aerobic speed (MAS) is the minimum running speed where maximum oxygen uptake occurs (Haugen *et al.*, 2014; Baker and Heaney, 2015). Thus, MAS is a useful performance test for estimating aerobic capacity and thus monitoring and prescribing training loads (Walker, 2016b). The suggested optimal distance to predict MAS in females is 1.4-1.5 km (Lundquist *et al.*, 2021a) and is the most recommended distance for measuring MAS within team sports (Thron *et al.*, 2024). Similar to assessments of power and speed, MAS results demonstrate that female football players who are more mature than younger adolescents have an increased maximal aerobic capacity (Mota *et al.*, 2002; Mujika *et al.*, 2009; Haugen *et al.*, 2014; Emmonds *et al.*, 2018, 2020; Datson *et al.*, 2020) and is associated with the increase in oxygen uptake which occurs as individuals attain PHV (Malina, Bouchard and Bar-Or, 2004).

2.2.4 Functional Movement Screening

The Functional Movement Screen (FMS) (Cook *et al.*, 2014a) is deemed to be widely used within the sport and exercise science field as well as in the general population (Davidson *et al.*, 2022). A FMS is the most common battery of tests when assessing movement ability in athletes (Lloyd *et al.*, 2015; Monaco and Schoenfeld, 2019; Davidson *et al.*, 2022). Initially, it was intended to assess flexibility, strength, imbalances or asymmetries between right and left limbs and general movement as prerequisites of athletic performance (Cook, Burton and Hoogenboom, 2006; Lloyd *et al.*, 2015). It is completed using a variety of performance tests (Cook, Burton and Hoogenboom, 2006; Lloyd *et al.*, 2015) with fundamental movement patterns being observed throughout (Cook *et al.*, 2014a; Eltoukhy *et al.*, 2016). However, it is now also used to reduce injury risk and support rehabilitation through observing and focusing on weaknesses or limb imbalances (Cook *et al.*, 2014a; Lloyd *et al.*, 2015). Cook's FMS (Cook *et al.*, 2014a) is comprised of seven movements: deep squat, hurdle step, forward in-line lunge, shoulder mobility, straight leg raise, trunk stability push-up and rotatory stability. It is

assessed on a scale of zero-to-three (zero = pain when completing the movement, one = the athlete cannot complete the movement, two = the athlete can complete the movement with a degree of compensation to do so, and three = the participant can complete the movement correctly) (Cook, Burton and Hoogenboom, 2006; Elphinston, 2008; Davidson *et al.*, 2022).

The FMS is a valuable tool to assess and support rehabilitation of knee injuries within sport (Eltoukhy *et al.*, 2016), where a poor FMS score is associated with an increased chance of non-contact injuries (McCall *et al.*, 2014; McCunn *et al.*, 2016). In male football players, FMS scores are noted to increase alongside PHV (Lloyd *et al.*, 2015; Portas *et al.*, 2016; Marques *et al.*, 2017; Silva *et al.*, 2017). In contrast, PHV has no significant impact on FMS scores in under-13 and -14 football players with a variety of score fluctuations between movements (MacMaster *et al.*, 2021). During childhood and adolescence, where the biggest developments in functional ability occur, increased change can be seen during completion of the FMS throughout this period (MacMaster *et al.*, 2021). Sex-specific comparisons between male and female footballer players have reported no significant differences in overall FMS scores (Paszkevicz, McCarty and Van Lunen, 2013; Chimera, Smith and Warren, 2015; Martín-Moya *et al.*, 2023). However, both males and females have an increased FMS score in relation to maturation (Paszkevicz, McCarty and Van Lunen, 2013). When examining the effects of pubertal changes in females during running, females in the later stages of pubertal development had higher knee flexion and adduction during running (Sayer *et al.*, 2018) and females with a higher FMS are associated with a faster sprint time (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). There is still a lack of information surrounding the impact BM has on youth female football player's FMS and performance metrics. This advocates the need for more research to allow a better understanding of how to support these athletes during this developmental period.

2.3 Video Analysis

High performance sport is hugely multi-factorial and the use of technology is one element to evaluate performance and enhance training regimes (Rangasamy *et al.*, 2020; Frevel, Beiderbeck and Schmidt, 2022). With advancements in technology constantly being developed, the ability to analyse sporting performance has become even more detailed (Barris and Button, 2008; Rangasamy *et al.*, 2020; Bunker and Susnjak, 2022). Video analysis has gained vast interest in the sporting world (Tuyls *et al.*, 2021) with its use in evaluating performance at amateur and elite level (Rangasamy *et al.*, 2020). Data is collected by cameras connected to analysis software, providing the ability to evaluate a specific skill or movement pattern (for example, gait analysis) (Barris and Button, 2008; van der Kruk and Reijne, 2018). Due to the advancements in technology, video analysis is now possible in most sports (Payton and Burden, 2018). It can be used to track athlete's performance metrics (for example an athlete's sprint or change of direction speed), on and off the playing field, along with equipment trajectories

(for example the ball kick trajectory in football), and an athlete's rehabilitation and return-to-play protocols (Rana and Mittal, 2021).

2.3.1 Vicon Motion Capture System

Motion capture is the ability to record and process human movement through the use of camera GPS (Metcalf *et al.*, 2013; van der Kruk and Reijne, 2018). There are multiple camera-based motion capture systems available, with the Vicon Motion Capture System (Oxford Metrics Group Ltd., Oxford, UK) regarded as the most widely used method of analysing biomechanical movements through a high-speed camera-based system (Menolotto *et al.*, 2020; Choo, Chow and Komar, 2022). The system is the most commonly used across multiple sports, ranging from tennis to taekwondo (Pueo Ortega and Jiménez Olmedo, 2017). The three-dimensional (3D) nature of the camera-based system is deemed the 'gold standard' methods for motion capture due to its accuracy and reliability (Metcalf *et al.*, 2013).

Vicon requires multiple two-dimensional cameras to be set up around the testing area to track human movement (Payton and Burden, 2018; Goldfarb *et al.*, 2021) and retroreflective markers to be placed on the skin or over items of tight-fitting clothing on anatomical landmarks creating reference points for data collection (Tabakin, 2000; van der Kruk and Reijne, 2018; Adesida, Papi and McGregor, 2019; Choo, Chow and Komar, 2022). The Helen Hayes marker set-up is widely used for lower body marker placement to complete data collection with the ability to track markers in a three-dimensional space providing accuracy in results (Tabakin, 2000; Houck, Yack and Cuddeford, 2004; Collins *et al.*, 2009; Kerkhoff, Wagner and Peikenkamp, 2020). Each marker must be seen by at least two cameras throughout the full data collection period to allow for marker positioning in the three-dimensional space (Payton and Burden, 2018).

Marker occlusion is one of the most challenging issues to overcome with motion capture testing (Islam *et al.*, 2020; Choo, Chow and Komar, 2022; Acevedo, Rekabdar and Mousas, 2023). Various studies report issues with marker occlusion when assessing hip, knee and ankle flexion during lower body dynamic movements with the Vicon or other similar systems due to the nature of the exercises completed (Szczerbik and Kalinowska, 2011; Young, 2019; Ota *et al.*, 2020; Goldfarb *et al.*, 2021). Errors occurring during kinematic data collection are strongly correlated with the misplacement and occlusion of markers (Szczerbik and Kalinowska, 2011; Young, 2019). Due to the fast-paced nature of most sports, highly dynamic movements can be difficult to capture (van der Kruk and Reijne, 2018) and marker occlusion can become a problem during analysis of movements (Choo, Chow and Komar, 2022). Gap filling is a tool which can overcome the issue of marker occlusion where the system determines marker trajectory during the occluded phase based on either marker trajectory before and after occlusion, movement of that marker in an earlier or later identical movement (e.g. a gait cycle)

where it was not occluded, or based on movement of a similar marker (e.g. on the same segment) (Goldfarb *et al.*, 2021). However, markers can be mislabelled or reconstructed resulting in invalid or errors in the data (Camargo *et al.*, 2020).

The use of the Vicon system requiring retroreflective marker placement and traditionally the need for indoor laboratory facilities negating the ability to perform the movement being assessed in a natural sporting environment (Pueo Ortega and Jiménez Olmedo, 2017; Payton and Burden, 2018; Adesida, Papi and McGregor, 2019; Taborri *et al.*, 2020). The system also requires the need for specialised or trained personnel to conduct the testing to ensure accuracy of the data being collected (Szczerbik and Kalinowska, 2011; Payton and Burden, 2018). However, this has been overcome by the use of systems with marker-less technology (Taborri *et al.*, 2020; Chidambaram *et al.*, 2022).

2.3.2 HumanTrak Movement Analysis System

Marker-less systems provide the ability to monitor athletes throughout sport, offering almost instantaneous feedback to athletes and providing real-time information about their movements within the sport which marker-based systems cannot offer (Adesida, Papi and McGregor, 2019; McCarthy *et al.*, 2023). Marker-less technology consists of a single motion capture camera (McPherson *et al.*, 2017), using advanced models of the human body and machine algorithms (Colyer *et al.*, 2018) offering a reliable, fast and cost-effective method for biomechanical analysis within the playing field (Umek and Kos, 2018; Rana and Mittal, 2021; Choo, Chow and Komar, 2022). This method can provide analysis on different movements performed by an athlete, and the relationship between an athlete and the equipment used within a given sport (Rum *et al.*, 2021).

An Australian Company, Vald Performance (Australian Catholic University and Vald Performance, 2021) introduced a marker-less motion analysis system named HumanTrak Movement Analysis System. HumanTrak Movement Analysis System, also referred to as HumanTrak, was brought to market in 2019 (Sinha, 2019; VALD, 2022) for the analysis of human movement (McCarthy *et al.*, 2023). HumanTrak captures data through marker-less tracking utilising a single Microsoft Azure Kinect DK Camera (Microsoft Corp. Redmond, WA, USA) and provides a platform to collect and analyse biomechanical data on human movement (McCarthy *et al.*, 2023). The system does not require specialist personnel in order to conduct the data collection due to the simplistic nature of the system, making it easy to understand and user-friendly (Young, 2019; Ota *et al.*, 2020). HumanTrak can be used to assess range of motion, stability, balance, and quality of movement using a 3D dynamic model of the participant, allowing almost instantaneous feedback to be given (Bates, *et al.*, 2017; McCarthy *et al.*, 2023). This assessment of human movement provides and monitors progress of each individual throughout the season for training and competition, and for rehabilitation or pre-habilitation programming (Bates, *et al.*, 2017).

Like all new technologies developed, the HumanTrak system must be validated to provide practitioners with confidence when reviewing the output data. Previous literature has reported HumanTrak to be a reliable system when measuring shoulder, hip and knee range of movement, and hip and knee flexion during squatting exercises, in both male and female participants, against validated biomechanical analysis measures; such as motion capture systems and goniometers (Schmitz *et al.*, 2015; Beshara *et al.*, 2020a; Australian Catholic University and Vald Performance, 2021; McCarthy *et al.*, 2023). In contrast, Microsoft Kinect (camera software used within HumanTrak) had poor validity and reliability against the Vicon Nexus system when assessing ankle, hip and knee flexion and knee adduction during lower body walking gait analysis, in both male and female participants (Mentiplay *et al.*, 2015). Due to the two-dimensional nature of the Microsoft Kinect camera, positioning of the system may have impacted joint angle assessment compared to the 3D system (Asadi and Arjmand, 2020). The movement being performed were completed in more than one plane as a result of, for example, joint rotation, movement towards/away from the camera and therefore using a single 2D camera may not provide true results due to only capturing data in the frontal plane (Maykut *et al.*, 2015; Lopes *et al.*, 2018). The study by Mentiplay *et al.* (2015) only analysed walking gait and, therefore, more research is required using different ranges of movement within multiple sports. Further studies on lower-limb movements should be conducted to validate the use of HumanTrak movement analysis and the Microsoft Azure Kinect camera used within the HumanTrak system for data collection in the field due to the novelty of the technology.

2.4 Aims and Objectives

This thesis had two research aims.

Firstly, to validate Vald Performance's marker-less motion capture system, HumanTrak, against the 'gold standard' Vicon Motion Capture system through the use of double- and single-limb dynamic movements in both male and female participants. It was hypothesised the system would have a moderate to high inter-class correlation to the Vicon Nexus system suggesting HumanTrak to be a valid system which can be used in the field to assess fundamental movements for athletic performance. The research would give practitioners a greater understanding of the HumanTrak marker-less system given its cost-effective, ease of access and ability to use it within a field-based environment in comparison to a Vicon system.

Secondly, to longitudinally track the effects of biological maturation against performance metrics of range of movement, power, speed and aerobic fitness in a Scottish female football academy. It was hypothesised early maturing players would have increased performance metrics than later maturing

players within the same team and performance metrics may fluctuate around PHV. It was suggested players going through PHV would have varying results on performance due to periods of rapid limb growth having a negative impact on performance. The findings from this research hopes to better inform practitioners of how to support youth female athletes during this period of adolescent awkwardness and provide insight into the changes which may be seen in performance metrics as a result of period of growth and maturation.

Chapter 3: Validity of HumanTrak Movement Analysis System for lower body functional movements.

3.1 Introduction

The use of technology and the desire to track and analyse human location in the field of sport and exercise science is growing (Wei *et al.*, 2021). Motion capture systems track and analyse human locomotion through retroreflective markers located on anatomical landmarks of the body (Raghu *et al.*, 2019; Goldfarb *et al.*, 2021). Three-dimensional motion capture systems use multiple connected, two-dimensional (2D) cameras to analyse human locomotion, whereas, 2D motion capture systems only use one or multiple unlinked cameras (Raghu *et al.*, 2019; Goldfarb *et al.*, 2021). Despite 3D systems being recognised as a gold standard measurement, they often are costly and require time-consuming processes, both in participant, system, and environment preparation as well as data analysis, and data capture is generally laboratory-based (Harsted *et al.*, 2019).

In contrast, marker-less motion capture systems have the potential to lessen these barriers and translate the application to real-world field based testing, as they are generally less costly, and are much less time intensive (McCarthy *et al.*, 2023). Despite the more wide-spread use of such systems in sport to evaluate athletes' technique and performance, conduct injury risk assessments and characterise movements/identify skill level (Adesida, Papi and McGregor, 2019) the validation of marker-less motion capture systems is lacking (Pino-Ortega *et al.*, 2022b). HumanTrak Movement Analysis System (VALD Performance, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia) is a marker-less motion capture system which has been used to track and assess functional and fundamental movements used within a range of different environments including rehabilitation, sporting and in clinical settings (Adesida, Papi and McGregor, 2019; Beshara *et al.*, 2020b). The marker-less system improves time efficiency of testing and provides instantaneous feedback to users on measured outcomes such as joint angles, range of motion and joint imbalances (McCarthy *et al.*, 2023). However, studies evaluating the validity of this system, to our knowledge, are limited in number, types of movements tested, and participant cohort size (Beshara *et al.*, 2020b; Australian Catholic University and Vald Performance, 2021).

In order to warrant application within a sporting environment, the system needs to be valid. Previously, the validity of HumanTrak was evaluated for shoulder flexion and abduction against a goniometer and it was deemed to be a valid measure for these joint movements with mean differences of less than five degrees (Beshara *et al.*, 2020b). Additionally, data produced by the HumanTrak manufacturer demonstrated excellent correlation for knee flexion between HumanTrak and a 3D system (Vicon) for single leg squats, although findings are based on only four participants. Therefore, the aim of this study was to validate the HumanTrak Movement Analysis System (VALD

Performance) against the Vicon Motion Analysis System (Vicon Nexus) for knee motion during double- and single-leg squats.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Participants

Twenty healthy adults (10 male and 10 female; age, 24 ± 3 years, body mass; 72.9 ± 15.8 kg, height; 172.1 ± 9.9 cm) participated in the study. Participants were accustomed to recreational exercise and had no prior lower-limb injuries in the last six months. All participants gave their written consent and completed a Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire prior to participation. The study was granted ethical approval from the School of Health and Life Science Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland (ethics number 18127-15437), conforming to the Declaration of Helsinki.

3.2.2 Data Collection

Participants attended a temperature-controlled laboratory (20.9°C) and wore tight fitting, non-reflective clothing. Leg length (in centimetres) was measured in a standing position, using a standard plastic measuring tape with measurements taken from the anterior superior iliac crest (ASIS) to the distal medial malleolus. Knee width (from medial to lateral femoral condyle) and ankle width (from medial and lateral malleolus) measured in centimetres was obtained using steel Vernier Callipers. Retroreflective markers were placed on their lower limbs following a Modified Helen Hayes marker set-up (Bakke and Besier, 2022). In brief, twenty markers were placed using double-sided tape (Sensi-Tak Hair System Tape, Sensi-Tak) to the left and right: anterior superior iliac crest, mid-point of the posterior superior iliac spine, front side of the thigh, lateral femoral condyle, medial femoral condyle, tibial tuberosity, mid-way along the fibula of the shank, lateral malleolus of the fibula, medial malleolus of the tibia, first toe, and heel (Figure 1) (Bakke and Besier, 2022). The same researcher measured leg length and joint width and placed the markers on all the participants for consistency. The researcher was taught by an International Society for the Advancement of Kinanthropometry (ISAK) accredited individual and then undertook five laboratory and protocol familiarisation sessions before completing any data collection to ensure they were accustomed to the equipment and the procedures.

Figure 1: Modified Helen Hays marker set-up in an anterior (A), lateral (B) and posterior (C) view.

Participants undertook a 10-minute warm-up consisting of a 5-minute light jog, followed by 5 minutes of dynamic stretches mainly focusing on the lower limbs including hip range of motion exercises (leg swings, squats and lunges). Data was then collected from a 9-camera Vicon Motion Analysis System (Version 2.11.0, 6. Oxford Industrial Park, Yarnton, Oxford, England, OX5 1QU) and a HumanTrak Movement Analysis System with a Microsoft Azure Kinect 3D infrared Camera (VALD Performance, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia). Participants chose their preferred, most comfortable (dominant) limb and performed (a) double-leg overhead squat (OHS) with a lightweight pole held above head, legs shoulder width apart, and heels fixed to the ground with squat depth as low as possible and (b) dominant limb single-leg squat (SLS) with hands crossed onto shoulders, and with the non-dominant leg held at 90 degrees hip flexion (Figure 2). Participants were instructed to attempt to keep knees over toes and squat as deeply as possible, ensuring the heel of the foot/feet on the ground does not lift in either exercise. Participants completed three sets of three repetitions of each exercise with a one-minute rest between each set. Knee flexion values were obtained for both the OHS and SLS and knee varus/valgus values for the SLS.

A

B

Figure 2: Participant completing both an overhead squat (OHS) exercise (A) and a single leg squat (SLS) exercise (B). Knee flexion is obtained in Vicon through the x axis and knee varus/valgus in the y axis.

A repetition was deemed successful if the following criteria was met: all markers were visible on the Vicon system, the participant's full body was always visible by the HumanTrak system and centre of mass remained within the target zone (participants centre of mass "marker" remained inside the bullseye zone which was visible on the systems screen) throughout the period of exercise tests (shown in Figure 3).

A

B

Figure 3: Target Zone on HumanTrak which participant must complete all exercises within.

3.2.3 Data Analysis

The middle repetition from the middle set of trials was used for data analysis for fifteen participants. For the remaining five participants, the first repetition from the middle set of trials was used due to a large period of marker occlusion rendering the middle repetition unsuitable for any data analysis. The HumanTrak knee flexion and varus/valgus values were reported in the system software and exported into a comprehensive comma-separated values (CSV) Microsoft Excel file. The Vicon data was analysed using Nexus software (Version 2.11.0, 6. Oxford Industrial Park, Yarnton, Oxford, England, OX5 1QU). Data were gap filled using Pattern fill and processed using the Plug-in gait and Woltering filter. Using the Vicon global coordinate system, movement in the x-axis related to knee flexion with positive values denoting greater knee flexion angles, and movement in the Y-axis related to knee varus/valgus with positive values denoting knee varus and the negative values denoting knee valgus (Figure 2). The largest knee flexion angles were extracted from both systems for knee flexion data for both OHS and SLS, and knee varus/valgus data was extracted at the point of greatest knee flexion from both systems for SLS as this is most commonly where the largest value of knee valgus occurs (Saki *et al.*, 2022). Knee varus/valgus data is not available for OHS in the HumanTrak system hence this could not be evaluated.

3.2.4 Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using Jamovi (version 2.3.28). Descriptive statistics were reported for participants characteristics and knee angles: knee flexion for OHS and SLS, and knee varus/valgus for SLS. The normality of data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-wilk test and via inspection of

histograms. Wilcoxon paired sample t-tests with 95% confidence intervals were used to compare knee angles between HumanTrak Movement Analysis System and Vicon Motion Analysis System. Bland-Altman Plots were generated to depict level of agreement for knee angles between the HumanTrak Movement Analysis System and the Vicon Motion Analysis System with 95% confidence intervals (CI) of limits of agreement (Bland and Altman, 1986; Schoonjans, 2022). Spearman’s correlation coefficient were used to examine the relationship between the HumanTrak and Vicon systems. Correlation coefficients are described as very large ($R \geq 0.07$), large ($R = 0.7 - 0.5$), moderate ($R = 0.5 - 0.3$) and small ($R = 0.3 - 0.1$) (Hopkins *et al.*, 2009). Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$.

3.3 Results

Participants’ knee flexion and varus/valgus (median \pm interquartile range) for the OHS and SLS are presented in Table 1. In all variables, no significant differences were observed between HumanTrak and Vicon systems in the Wilcoxon paired t-test as $p > 0.05$ (See Table 1).

Table 1: Participants’ descriptive data, and knee flexion and varus/valgus angles for HumanTrak and Vicon for overhead squat (OHS) and single-leg squat (SLS).

	Median \pm IQR		p Value
	HumanTrak System	Vicon System	
Knee Flexion ($^{\circ}$)			
OHS	98.65 \pm 25.48	99.55 \pm 28.08	0.956
SLS	79.70 \pm 19.45	72.90 \pm 15.70	0.388
Knee Varus/Valgus ($^{\circ}$)			
SLS	7.40 \pm 4.75	8.30 \pm 15.93	0.330

N = 20, age = 24 \pm 3 years, body mass = 72.6 \pm 15.8 kg, standing height = 172.1 \pm 9.9 cm

SD; Standard Deviation, kg; kilograms, cm; centimetres, IQR; Interquartile Range, OHS;

Overhead Squat, SLS; Single-leg Squat, $^{\circ}$; degrees.

Table 2: Comparative results of knee flexion and varus/valgus obtained from HumanTrak and Vicon systems during overhead (OHS) and single-leg (SLS) squats.

	Vicon (Mean±SD)	HumanTrak (Mean±SD)	Mean Difference (SD)	Lower LoA (95 % CI)	Upper LoA (95 % CI)	r	p
Knee Flexion (°)							
OHS	95.05 ± 28.90	97.12 ± 23.46	-2.07 (17.30)	-35.98 (-50.1 to -21.91)	31.84 (17.8 to 45.92)	0.843	< 0.001*
SLS	75.27 ± 24.08	77.91 ± 15.47	-2.64 (18.12)	-38.15 (-52.9 to -23.41)	32.88 (18.1 to 47.63)	0.683	< 0.001*
Knee Varus/Valgus (°)							
SLS	9.08 ± 17.17	5.94 ± 5.94	3.13 (15.89)	-28.00 (-40.92 to -15.1)	34.27 (21.35 to 47.2)	0.104	0.663

OHS; Overhead Squat, SLS; Single-leg Squat, LoA; Limits of agreement, CI; 95% Confidence Intervals, r; Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient, p; correlation p-value,*; statistical significance (p < 0.05).

Figure 4 shows the Bland-Altman plots for peak knee flexion values during an OHS (Fig 4a), SLS (Fig 4b) and knee varus/valgus values obtained during peak knee flexion during the SLS (Fig 4c). Differences (bias) (solid line) and 95% limits of agreement (dashed line) were determined and illustrated between the HumanTrak and Vicon systems. Table 2 also reports the comparative results for knee flexion and varus/valgus from the HumanTrak and Vicon systems during both the OHS and SLS.

There were no systematic bias for OHS and SLS knee flexion, as bias lines and points are close to zero (OHS knee flexion: -2.07°, SLS knee flexion: -2.64°). The limits of agreement (LoA) are wide with variability between the two systems (OHS knee flexion: LoA between -35.98° (95% CI [-50.10° to -21.91°]) and 31.84° (95% CI [17.80° to 45.92°]), SLS knee flexion: LoA between -38.15° (95% CI [-52.90° to -23.41°]) and 32.88° (95% CI [18.10° to 47.63°])). A trend between the two systems for SLS knee varus/valgus demonstrates as the means between the two systems increases, the difference increases (SLS knee varus/valgus: 3.14°, LoA between -28.00° (95% CI [-40.92° to -15.10°]) and 34.27° (95% CI [21.35° to 47.20°])). As a result of the wide LoA during both OHS and SLS comparison between the two systems is not recommended. However, as the mean bias is low in both OHS and SLS trials comparison

between the two systems is appropriate (shown in Table 2). Additionally, in Figure 4c, proportional bias appears at approximately 10° displaying that after this point the difference between both HumanTrak and Vicon becomes increasingly larger as the mean increases.

Figure 4: Analysis of agreement between HumanTrak and Vicon using Bland-Altman plots. A: Peak knee flexion during the overhead squat (OHS). B: Peak knee flexion of the dominant limb during the single leg squat (SLS). C: Knee varus (positive) or valgus (negative) value at the greatest point of knee flexion during the single leg squat (SLS). The solid line signifies mean difference (bias) between the two systems and the dashed lines signifies the upper and lower limits of agreement ($\pm 1.96SD$).

There was a significant positive correlation between the two systems for OHS knee flexion ($r = 0.843$, $p < 0.001$) and SLS knee flexion ($r = 0.683$, $p < 0.001$), see Figure 5 a, b. No significant correlation was found between the two systems for knee varus/valgus during the SLS ($r = 0.104$, $p = 0.663$), see Figure 5c.

Figure 5: Relationship between HumanTrak and Vicon using correlation coefficients. A: Peak knee flexion during the overhead squat (OHS). B: Peak knee flexion of the dominant limb during the single leg squat (SLS). C: Knee varus (positive) or valgus (negative) value at the greatest point of knee flexion during the single leg squat (SLS).

3.4 Discussion

The purpose of the study was to compare VALD Performance's HumanTrak Movement Analysis System to Vicon Nexus's Motion Analysis System for knee angles during OHS and SLS. The HumanTrak Movement Analysis System had a significant relationship when compared to Vicon Motion Analysis system for both double- and single-leg squats when assessing knee flexion, however, the LoA between the two systems is large suggesting high variability between trials. The HumanTrak system is inaccurate at comparing knee varus/valgus in SLS movements.

From the present study, HumanTrak reported similar results to the Vicon system for OHS and SLS knee flexion, with a good level of agreement between the two systems. There was a statistically significant relationship between the two systems for knee flexion when participants completed an OHS and SLS, thus suggesting it is a valid method of marker-less motion capture at collection values of knee flexion. To the best of our knowledge, the only validation study for HumanTrak was conducted on upper limb movements (Beshara *et al.*, 2020b) which reported HumanTrak to be an accurate measure of the shoulder with results reporting a significant positive relationship in shoulder flexion (free $r = 0.77$; fixed $r = 0.96$) and abduction (fixed $r = 0.87$) when compared to a goniometer (Beshara *et al.*, 2020b). However, the use of a manual universal goniometer as a "gold standard" measure is questionable due to the repeatability of the measurement and dependency of the assessor's skill level, although being deemed as a more cost-effective method (Svensson, Lind and Löfgren Harringe, 2019; Kraus *et al.*, 2020). Completing a similar study within lower body functional movements of the OHS or SLS at both fixed and free movement may be able to provide greater insight into the validity of the HumanTrak System. Various studies have compared Microsoft Kinect marker-less cameras (used within the HumanTrak system) to Vicon motion capture during gait assessing knee flexion (Pfister *et al.*, 2014; Mentiplay *et al.*, 2015; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2019). The Kinect system was deemed valid and accurate if Kinect cameras were used to assess knee flexion during gait analysis (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2019). The study by Rodrigues *et al.* (2019) used four calibrated and connected Kinect cameras to collect and analyse human movement which is more cameras used than in this present study. However, Rodrigues *et al.* (2019) assessed moving gait and not movements in area set position. Similarly, a strong agreement in lower body squatting movements of knee and hip flexion, adduction and internal rotation between a marker-less Microsoft Kinect camera and Eagle motion camera-based system was reported (Schmitz *et al.*, 2015). The study by Schmitz *et al.* (2015) did not use the Vicon Capture system as the 'gold standard' method of data collection and therefore should be treated with caution when comparing to the current study. Conversely, the consensus of comparing the Kinect Camera and Vicon system suggest the Kinect camera should not be used in clinical settings due to the high variability of the Kinect system within individual studies (Pfister *et al.*, 2014; Mentiplay *et al.*, 2015). Each of these

studies used different set-ups for marker set-up and placement (Collins *et al.*, 2009; Vicon Motion Systems Limited, 2016) which could have an impact on the results obtained. Further research into the validation of HumanTrak system against the Vicon system for both upper and lower movements would be able to provide a more concise understand as to whether this is a valid tool to be using in the field.

In the current study, HumanTrak over- and in some cases, under-reported values of knee varus/valgus in comparison to the Vicon system. In contrast, published validation data by VALD Performance investigated knee varus/valgus through the frontal plane projection angle within a SLS movement, which reported a mean difference of 1.2 degrees between HumanTrak and Vicon and a good to excellent significant correlation ($R = 0.9829$), stating a high validity between the two systems (Australian Catholic University and Vald Performance, 2021). The results produced by VALD validating the HumanTrak system over reported knee varus/valgus angles in most instances by ~ 2 degrees. The results from this current study and the validation data published by VALD ask participants to squat 'as low as possible' which could be a different ROM ability and therefore provide different squat depths for every participant. More validation data collect should be conducted to give a greater, more succinct understanding of the accuracy of the HumanTrak system both in free and fixed knee flexion during lower body movements of the OHS and SLS and to assess hip flexion to understand any effect this may have on the results obtained. Likewise, results produced from a marker-less system, Theia 3D, are similar when compared to Vicon during gait analysis using the Plug-in gait marker set-up (Wren, Isakov and Rethlefsen, 2023). However, these results are in contrast with results from this current study due to knee varus/valgus values reported to have a high variability between HumanTrak and Vicon. The wide limits of agreement in the results of the current study suggest high variability between the two systems which in practice might impact of interpretation of results, for example, levels of asymmetry in lower limbs of athletes or rehabilitation assessments for athletes. This proposes the need for additional validation data assessing knee varus/valgus in order to draw firm conclusions from the HumanTrak marker-less system. This would allow practitioners to confidently use this system in an applied setting to maximise athlete testing, movement assessment and injury risk. Knee flexion during both OHS and SLS appear to have higher validity than SLS knee varus/valgus which could be a result of HumanTrak collecting data in the frontal plane. This may impact the data collected on knee varus/valgus due to not having movement capture systems collecting data from a lateral view. Also, the difference between 2D and 3D for knee valgus/varus is likely that 2D cannot accurately measure out plane movement such as knee valgus when movement is recorded in a frontal plane as knee valgus incorporates femur internal rotation.

This study is not without limitations. The study tested 20 participants who were recreationally active in OHS and SLS exercises. Further grouping of participants by sex, due to the biological differences between males and females, might have produced different results in the Bland-Altman plots and correlations and therefore should be taken into consideration for future studies. Leg length was also obtained using a plastic measuring tape in the current study, future research should use a steel measuring tape to measure leg length as this is considered 'gold standard'. The HumanTrak system should be tested under more dynamic lower body movements (for example, countermovement jumps or lunges) to assess whether validity is similar in these movement patterns. It is also important to note, this study did not obtain the range of motion of participants to assess any delay between skeletal growth and musculo-tendon. This could be a future direction of subsequent research to further understand any effects of growth on lower body movements. All three trials with each participant were completed within the one laboratory testing session, further research into inter- and intra-day reliability should be conducted to assess the reliability of set-up variation. Finally, this study does not utilise inertial sensors within HumanTrak when assessing variables. This could have impacted accuracy of results obtained and future research should assess the validity of the HumanTrak, using inertial sensors, for lower-limb movements (Beshara *et al.*, 2020).

3.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, for values of knee flexion in both the OHS and SLS similar results are obtained between the HumanTrak and Vicon systems, with similar margins or error, suggesting HumanTrak to be a valid system when assessing values of knee flexion in the field. There was no relationship, and a large difference reported for knee varus/valgus between HumanTrak and Vicon during SLS. More testing of the VALD Performance's HumanTrak Movement Analysis system is required to assess its validity at measuring peak knee flexion and knee varus/valgus due to only obtaining a moderate relationship compared to the Vicon system. Future research should investigate similar parameters to this study with the use of additional synchronised Microsoft Kinect cameras to assess the reliability of the marker-less system in multiple planes. The findings from this study will allow researchers an informed understanding of the validity of the HumanTrak system on lower body functional movements with the information from this current thesis.

Chapter 4: Tracking of performance variables with respect to maturation status in female academy football players over the course of one soccer season.

4.1 Introduction

Biological Maturation (BM) is an important factor in any sporting environment and is the time and process of a child to change and grow to reach adult state. These changes are psychological, behavioural, physiological and anatomical (Sherar *et al.*, 2010; Fernández-Galván *et al.*, 2021), with the maturation process differing for every child (Baxter-Jones, Thompson and Malina, 2002). With a recent exponential increase in participation of women's football, both at professional and youth level, it is necessary to know what effect BM can have on sporting performance (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Mainer-Pardos *et al.*, 2021). Biological maturation is a factor which can be influenced during the selection process as early maturing athletes are seen to have a higher chance of selection (Müller *et al.*, 2015). Biological Maturation can be assessed through skeletal age, dental age and peak height velocity (PHV) (Baxter-Jones, Thompson and Malina, 2002), however, PHV can be assessed through somatic, non-invasive measurement which use anthropometric measurements and is described as the most rapid period of growth (in height) during adolescent years (Baxter-Jones, Thompson and Malina, 2002; Malina *et al.*, 2015b; Sluis *et al.*, 2015). Two main non-invasive approaches are the Khamis–Roche Method (Khamis and Roche, 1994; Malina *et al.*, 2019) and the Mirwald Predictive Equation (Baxter-Jones, Thompson and Malina, 2002; Mirwald *et al.*, 2002). An improved equation for males, the Fransen equation (Fransen *et al.*, 2018), has been introduced to develop the Mirwald equation through a maturity ratio (Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). Although this equation is still limited as there is no improved assessment for females.

Biological maturation in male athletes, and particularly in male football has been extensively studied (Spencer *et al.*, 2011; Gastin, Bennett and Cook, 2013; Peña-González *et al.*, 2018; Radnor *et al.*, 2021; King *et al.*, 2022a). Findings suggest physical performance metrics are affected by maturation status in academy level development and regional football (Peña-González *et al.*, 2018; Costa *et al.*, 2021; Radnor *et al.*, 2021). Faster sprint speed (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Asadi *et al.*, 2018; Peña-González *et al.*, 2018; Radnor *et al.*, 2021), higher jump height (Deprez *et al.*, 2013; Asadi *et al.*, 2018) and aerobic capacity (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Philippaerts *et al.*, 2006) have been reported in early maturing players compared to their later maturing counterparts.

In women's football, little is known about the impact maturation has on the performance metrics of youth female football players (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020). Profiling performance metrics with maturation

status of youth female footballers allows training programs to be developed to support maturing athletes (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Datson *et al.*, 2022; Harkness-Armstrong *et al.*, 2022), yet limited information supporting the impact of maturation on performance metrics makes it challenging for recommendations and programs to be established (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Mainer-Pardos *et al.*, 2021). The influence of maturation using the Mirwald predictive equation on several physical characteristics in female athletes from multiple sporting backgrounds have previously been evaluated (Taylor *et al.*, 2013; Prieske *et al.*, 2019). More biologically mature players are seen to having increased performance in metrics of sprint time, power output and agility (Taylor *et al.*, 2013; Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Almeida-Neto *et al.*, 2022; Datson *et al.*, 2022). Longitudinal data, specifically in adolescent female footballers, is not available (Baxter-Jones, Thompson and Malina, 2002; Emmonds *et al.*, 2020), however such data are becoming available in other sporting populations such as rowing (Almeida-Neto *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, the aim of the present study was to track performance metrics of knee varus/valgus, countermovement jump height, 30 m sprint time and 1.4 km maximal aerobic speed with respect to maturation status in female academy football players over the course of a nine-month period and identify any changes in performance which may occur. In doing so, it will provide a better understanding into the effects biological maturation has on performance and specifically for female adolescents within a football setting. It will also offer considerations surrounding talent identification processes, player selection and physical development for adolescent females within football due to growth and maturation.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Subjects

Ninety-five female soccer players (n=95; age, 14±2years) were recruited to participate on a voluntary basis. Participants were from a Scottish Youth Football Academy (under 10 years – under 18 years teams) and trained twice per week with sessions lasting between 1 - 1.5 hours and played a competitive match once per week. Participants were free from injury for three months prior to testing. Participants (and their legal guardian if under the age of sixteen) were sent participant information sheets and had the study fully explained to them by the principal investigator, followed by attaining assent and informed consent. This study was granted ethical approval from the School of Health and Life Science Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland (approval number 17238-15097), conforming to the Declaration of Helsinki.

4.2.2 Design

The study adopted a longitudinal observational design whereby participants attended four data collection sessions over a nine-month period (Figure 6). Due to 60% missing data for time point 2

because of sickness, injury and school holidays, this time point was omitted from analysis and the remaining time points re-named time point A, B, and C. Timepoint A represents baseline measurements collected during pre-season, timepoint B is measurements after a six-month period and timepoint C after a nine-month period at the end of the season. Data was collected in the teams' indoor and outdoor training facilities during standard 'testing sessions' in replacement of one training session, and therefore players were accustomed to the facilities and procedures. Anthropometric measurements, FMS and CMJ were all completed indoors, and the 30 m sprints and 1.4 km MAS were completed outdoors. This removed temperature as a variable factor for all indoor tests, however, due to the space available indoors 30 m sprint and 1.4 km MAS had to be completed outdoors. All testing sessions occurred at the same time of day for each of the academy teams with a maximum of a 7-day gap between indoor and outdoor testing. Environmental conditions were monitored using a Barometer (Oregon Scientific, Tualatin, Oregon, United States) with indoor air temperatures ranging between 16-18 °C and relative humidity 35%, and outdoor temperatures and relative humidity ranging between -3.3 to +14.5°C and 52-79%, respectively (Table 3).

Figure 6: Schematic of Study and Testing Session Overview with progression of testing for each age range.

Table 3: Average outdoor temperature in degrees Celsius (reported as a mean and standard deviation) for each age group at timepoint A (baseline), timepoint B (6-months) and timepoint C (9-months).

Team	TP A (Mean ± SD)		TP B (Mean ± SD)		TP C (Mean ± SD)		Range of Temperature Across all timepoints (minimum – maximum)	
	Temperature (°)	Humidity (%)	Temperature (°)	Humidity (%)	Temperature (°)	Humidity (%)	Temperature (°)	Humidity (%)
U10	8.30	75	8.80	79	8.10	79	8.10 – 8.80	75 - 79
U12	9.85 ± 0.21	71 ± 1.41	4.83 ± 5.96	74 ± 2.83	3.85 ± 1.06	60 ± 4.24	-1.2 – 10.1	57 - 76
U14	7.10 ± 3.68	68.67 ± 10.07	8.00 ± 3.54	78.5 ± 0.71	3.17 ± 5.60	61.67 ± 10.02	-2.4 – 12.2	52 - 79
U16	9.15 ± 1.20	72 ± 8.49	4.95 ± 0.78	76 ± 4.24	3.35 ± 7.72	74.5 ± 2.12	-4.3 – 10.5	66 - 79
U18	9.85 ± 0.21	72.5 ± 9.19	2.40 ± 5.01	75.7 ± 3.51	6.67 ± 2.97	65.67 ± 9.29	-3.3 – 10.5	58 - 79

TP, timepoint; SD, standard deviation

Participants completed a standardised 10-minute warm-up, consisting of a light jog and dynamic stretching exercises before participating in the testing protocols. During every indoor testing session, anthropometric measurements were obtained. Participants were weighed in light clothing with shoes removed using a SECA Scales (SECA, 40 Barn Street, Birmingham, United Kingdom, B5 5QB) recording body mass in kilograms (kg) to the nearest 0.1 kg. Seated and standing height were obtained in the Frankfurt position ((Warrier *et al.*, 2023) using a SECA Stadiometer (SECA, 40 Barn Street, Birmingham, United Kingdom, B5 5QB) with height recorded in centimetres (cm) to the nearest 1 cm. Elements of Cook's Functional Movement Screen™(FMS) (Cook *et al.*, 2014b) and McKeown's Athletic Ability Assessment (McKeown *et al.*, 2014) were completed by all participants, and this comprised of four functional movements; single leg balance, single leg squat (SLS), forward lunge and an overhead squat facing the HumanTrak Movement Analysis System (Vald Performance, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia). Functional movement screens are a tool used to monitor and assess fundamental movement patterns with the ability to track progressions in these movements over time. The four functional movements assessed were demonstrated by the principal investigator and participants were instructed on the test using standard cues (instructions to keep their heels on the ground throughout and chest upright). Each participant had the opportunity to perform practice trials to familiarise themselves with the exercises. Left and right varus/valgus values were reported at the point of peak knee flexion during the SLS. Following the functional movements, all participants completed a countermovement jump (CMJ) to assess jump height (in centimetres) recorded by HumanTrak Movement Analysis System (Vald Performance, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia). Participants aged 12 plus completed the full outdoor battery of tests; 30 m sprint, 1.4 km maximal aerobic speed (MAS) and answered a self-report Pubertal Development Scale (PDS). Participants aged 10 and 11 only completed the outdoor 30 m sprint. Younger participants are still developing the physical capabilities needed (e.g. motor function and muscle volume) to complete the 30 m sprint and 1.4 km MAS test, therefore an age limit was set on these exercise tests (O'Brien *et al.*, 2009; Mendez-Villanueva *et al.*, 2011). The age categories for each exercise test, shown in Figure 6, were determined by the Youth Physical Development Model (Lloyd and Oliver, 2012b). The Youth Physical Development Model offers a detailed approach to development on a sex specific basis and highlights the importance of physical development during periods of growth throughout adolescent development (Lloyd and Oliver, 2012b).

4.2.2.1 Countermovement Jump

Participants stood feet shoulder-width apart and were instructed to bend their knees into a half squat and immediately jump up as high as possible, extending the hip, knee and ankle joints. Participants were also instructed to attempt to land in the same position as take-off in a soft-landing position with their knees slightly bent (Walker, 2016a). Hands were to remain on hips for the duration of this test

to ensure comparable results were obtained. The HumanTrak system recorded jump height to the nearest 0.01 cm.

4.2.2.2 30 m Sprint

One practice 30 m sprint was completed before completing two attempts of the 30m sprints recorded using a Brower TCi Timing System; 4 tripods, 2 TCi PhotoGate A&B, 1 TCi motion start and 1 TCi timer (Brower Timing, Draper, Utah, USA). Participants started one meter behind the first timing gate and sprinted as fast as possible through the second set of timing gates without slowing down until they were fully past the gates. A 2-minute rest period was given to participants before completing their second attempt. The quickest time (to the nearest 0.01 second) was recorded for sprint time (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020).

4.2.2.3 1.4 km Maximal Aerobic Speed

The 1.4km MAS test (Lundquist *et al.*, 2021) involved participants running fourteen lengths of a 100 m pitch (equalling 1.4 km) as quickly possible. Participants were prompted to touch their foot on the line at each end and make a quick turn at each end. Feedback was provided to the participants on the number of 100 m lengths they had completed. Following completion of their final run, time was recorded to the nearest second.

4.2.2.4 Biological Maturation

4.2.2.4.1 Mirwald Predictive Equation

Biological Maturation was assessed using the Mirwald Predictive Equation (Mirwald *et al.*, 2002).

Maturity Offset (years)

$$\begin{aligned} &= -9.376 + (0.0001882 \times (\text{leg length} \times \text{seated height})) \\ &+ (0.0022 \times (\text{age} \times \text{leg length})) + (0.005841 \times (\text{age} \times \text{seated height})) \\ &- (0.002658 \times (\text{age} \times \text{weight})) + (0.07693 \times ((\frac{\text{weight}}{\text{height}}) \times 100)) \end{aligned}$$

Equation 1: Mirwald Predictive Equation for females.

The non-invasive method used body mass, standing and seated height to assess the age at which maturation occurs. Leg length was estimated using the calculation below (Malina and Koziel, 2014; Mainer-Pardos *et al.*, 2021).

$$\text{Leg Length} = \text{Standing Height} - \text{Seated Height}$$

Equation 2: Leg Length Calculation.

Peak Height Velocity (PHV) was calculated by subtracting age from maturity offset.

$$\text{Age at PHV (years)} = \text{Age} - \text{Maturity Offset}$$

Equation 3: Peak Height Velocity (PHV) Calculation.

4.2.2.4.2 Pubertal Development Scale

Pubertal status was assessed using an amended self-report Pubertal Development Scales (PDS) (Carskadon and Acebo, 1993). This is a non-invasive method of measuring pubertal status and consists of six questions for each participant, aged 12-18 (Vaishampayan and Deshpande, 2019). The PDS is a reliable self-report method with high association to Tanner stages of pubertal development (Emmanuel and Bokor, 2017; Koopman-Verhoeff *et al.*, 2020) and the scores recorded categorised participants from pre- to post-pubertal (Koopman-Verhoeff *et al.*, 2020). The PDS was completed by 17 participants and the data was split into two groups due to sample size; pre-menarche (P2 and P3) and post-menarche (P4 and P5).

4.2.4 Data Analysis

Data processing was conducted using Microsoft® Excel (Microsoft® Excel, Office365 for Windows 10 version 21H2, Microsoft Incorporation, Redmond, WA, U.S.A). From all data collected, participants who had missing maturity offset (MO) data were removed for analysis purposes. Participants with maturity data missing from more than two performance measurement timepoints were excluded in the statistical analysis due to being unable to longitudinally track their performance metrics in respect to maturation or compare any performance metrics collected at these timepoints to maturation data.

4.2.5 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using Jamovi (Jamovi, version 1.6, The Jamovi Project (2021)). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Distribution of data was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. A Repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine changes between all performance metrics of left and right knee valgus, CMJ height, 30 m sprint time and 1.4 km MAS across the nine-month period (three timepoints; A, B and C). A Pearsons Rank Coefficient was used to report the relationship between years to and from PHV (Y-PHV) and performance metrics of left and right knee valgus, CMJ height, 30m sprint time and 1.4km MAS over the six- and nine-month time periods from timepoint A. Correlation coefficients are described as very large ($R \geq 0.07$), large ($R = 0.7 - 0.5$), moderate ($R = 0.5 - 0.3$) and small ($R = 0.3 - 0.1$) (Hopkins *et al.*, 2009). An independent t-test was conducted to assess differences between performance metrics based on participants pubertal development scores (pre-menarche and post-menarche), at all three timepoints.

4.3 Results

Descriptive statistics (mean±SD) for maturity offset and performance metrics (timepoint A, timepoint B and timepoint C), and mean change in performance metrics and maturity offset (timepoint B minus timepoint A, and timepoint C minus timepoint A) with 95% confidence intervals are presented in Table 4. Maturity offset significantly increased across all three timepoints ($p < 0.001$). There were no significant differences for any performance metrics across the timepoints over the nine-month period (all $p > 0.05$).

Table 4: Maturity offset and performance metrics for all three testing timepoints from the repeated measures ANOVA. Timepoint (TP) A is baseline, Timepoint (TP) B is six months from baseline and timepoint (TP) C is nine months from baseline. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

	TP A (Mean \pm SD)	TP B (Mean \pm SD)	TP C (Mean \pm SD)	Mean change to TP B (95 % Confidence Intervals)	TP A Mean change A to TP C (95 % Confidence Intervals)	TP	p Value
N	47	67	65				
Outdoor Temperature (°C)	8.70 \pm 2.11	5.51 \pm 3.89	4.44 \pm 4.50	-4.24 (-10.43 to -6.19)	-3.16 (-7.79 to -4.63)		0.402
Maturity Offset	0.51 \pm 1.63	1.42 \pm 1.62	1.66 \pm 1.56	0.90 (0.81 to 0.99)	1.14 (1.04 to 1.24)		0.001*
SL Squat L Knee Valgus (°)	9.84 \pm 13.96	12.52 \pm 9.72	10.32 \pm 9.17	2.67 (0.9 to 4.45)	0.47 (-1.4 to 2.38)		0.294
SL Squat R Knee Valgus (°)	10.47 \pm 16.35	10.49 \pm 10.12	10.11 \pm 8.06	0.02 (-2.4 to 2.43)	-0.36 (-3.3 to 2.54)		0.130
CMJ Height (cm)	26.96 \pm 4.29	26.93 \pm 5.17	27.54 \pm 5.6	-0.03 (-0.1 to -0.1)	0.58 (0.4 to 0.7)		0.610
30 m Sprint Time (s)	5.17 \pm 0.47	5.55 \pm 3.71	5.55 \pm 3.68	0.38 (-0.38 to 1.15)	0.39 (-0.41 to 1.19)		0.402
1.4 km MAS (m/s)	3.79 \pm 0.29	3.63 \pm 0.47	3.55 \pm 0.49	-0.16 (-0.2 to -0.13)	-0.24 (-0.29 to -0.21)		0.058

TP, timepoint; N, number; SD, standard deviation; y, years; SL; single leg; °, degrees; cm, centimetres; s, seconds; MAS, maximal aerobic speed; m/s, metres per second; *, statistical significance

4.3.1 Single Leg Knee Valgus

At all three timepoints, single leg left knee varus/valgus was not associated with Y-PHV (timepoint A: $r = -0.112$, $p = 0.480$; timepoint B: $r = -0.272$, $p = 0.084$; timepoint C: $r = -0.133$, $p = 0.412$) (Figure 7). Single leg right knee varus/valgus at timepoint A had a moderate positive relationship with Y-PHV ($r = 0.382$, $p < 0.05$). At timepoints B and C, there was no statistical significance between single leg right knee varus/valgus and Y-PHV (timepoint B: $r = -0.091$, $p = 0.571$; timepoint C: $r = 0.023$, $p = 0.891$), Figure 7.

Figure 7: Relationship between years to- and from-PHV (Y-PHV) and single leg knee valgus (degrees) for both the left and right limbs at timepoint A (A), timepoint B (B) and timepoint C (C).

4.3.2 Countermovement Jump

There was a moderate positive relationship between CMJ and Y-PHV at timepoints A and C (timepoint A: $r = 0.375$, $p < 0.05$; timepoint C: $r = 0.487$, $p < 0.001$). No relationship was reported at timepoint B ($r = 0.184$, $p = 0.261$), shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Relationship between years to- and from-PHV (Y-PHV) and countermovement jump (CMJ) height (cm) at timepoint A (A), timepoint B (B) and timepoint C (C).

4.3.3 30 m Sprint Time

Across all three timepoints, 30 m sprint time had significantly large negative correlations with Y-PHV (TP A: $r = -0.628$, $p < 0.001$; TP B: $r = -0.556$, $p < 0.001$; TP C: $r = -0.596$, $p < 0.001$), shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Relationship between years to- and from-PHV (Y-PHV) and 30 m sprint time (seconds) at timepoint A (A), timepoint B (B) and timepoint C (C).

4.3.4 1.4 km Maximal Aerobic Speed

At timepoint C, 1.4km MAS (m/s) had a moderate positive relationship with Y-PHV ($r = 0.382$, $p = 0.012$). Both timepoints A and B had no relationship between 1.4km MAS (m/s) and Y-PHV (where $p > 0.05$), Figure 10. The lack of participants, specifically pre-PHV, at TP A and B could have affected the relationship observed during data analysis.

Figure 10: Relationship between years to- and from-PHV (Y-PHV) and 1.4 km maximal aerobic speed (MAS) (m/s) at timepoint A (A), timepoint B (B) and timepoint C (C).

At all three timepoints, the post-menarche group had a significantly lower 30 m sprint time compared to the pre-menarche group (timepoint A: $p = 0.013$; timepoint B: $p = 0.006$; timepoint C: $p = 0.003$). All other performance metrics at all timepoints noted no significant differences between pre-menarche and post-menarche groups ($p > 0.05$), illustrated in Table 5.

Table 5: Comparison of pre-menarche and post-menarche participants for all performance metrics at all three timepoints (mean \pm SD). Analysis is based on a split of pubertal development, with participants not yet reached menarche; pre-menarche (P2-P3) and participants having started menstruation; post-menarche (P4-P5). Statistical Significance noted where $p < 0.05$.

	Timepoint A			Timepoint B			Timepoint C		
	Pre-Menarche Mean \pm SD	Post-Menarche Mean \pm SD	p Value	Pre-Menarche Mean \pm SD	Post-Menarche Mean \pm SD	p Value	Pre-Menarche Mean \pm SD	Post-Menarche Mean \pm SD	p Value
N	8	10	-	8	18	-	10	18	-
Left SL Knee Valgus (°)	9.83 \pm 6.59	6.94 \pm 7.837	0.438	12.52 \pm 11.48	9.11 \pm 9.26	0.412	15.51 \pm 13.79	7.38 \pm 7.95	0.057
Right SL Knee Valgus (°)	4.99 \pm 8.87	12.81 \pm 6.92	0.051	11.97 \pm 8.87	10.16 \pm 10.15	0.654	9.45 \pm 5.73	8.61 \pm 7.46	0.761
CMJ Height (cm)	26.29 \pm 4.17	28.52 \pm 4.92	0.323	27.1 \pm 6.25	25.53 \pm 5.21	0.512	26.53 \pm 5.92	27.5 \pm 5.81	0.679
30 m Sprint Time (s)	5.26 \pm 0.32	4.84 \pm 0.28	0.013 *	5.34 \pm 0.53	4.88 \pm 0.29	0.006 *	5.33 \pm 0.57	4.8 \pm 0.28	0.003*
1.4 km MAS (m/s)	-	3.82 \pm 0.29	-	3.68 \pm 0.28	3.66 \pm 0.46	0.934	3.54 \pm 0.37	3.63 \pm 0.47	0.705

SD, standard deviation; °, degrees; cm, centimetres; s, seconds; MAS, maximal aerobic speed; m/s, metres per second.

* Statistical Significance, where $p < 0.05$.

4.4 Discussion

The aim of the present study was to track performance metrics over a nine-month period and to explore changes in performance metrics which may have been affected by BM. When assessing performance metrics, for all participants, over the course of nine-months there was no significant change in all metrics. However, the main findings highlight that BM significantly affects 30 m sprint time in academy female football players with more biologically mature players having a faster sprint time than their later maturing peers. Lower body power was increased in more mature players at timepoint A and C but not at timepoint B. Aerobic Capacity was improved in players further past Y-PHV than their less mature peers at timepoint C, but due to the lack of participants at timepoints A and B there was no change in aerobic capacity with maturation. Biological maturation had little to no effect on metrics of left and right knee valgus at any timepoint.

Firstly, assessing sprint time in relation to BM over the course of a nine-month period, showed sprint time to be reduced in players who were more biologically mature than their peers. At each timepoint, 30 m sprint time displayed a significant correlation with BM and significant differences between players pre- and post-menarche were also evident when assessing 30 m sprint data at all testing point. Therefore, demonstrating more biologically mature participants, both as a measure of Y-PHV and pubertal development are faster than less mature participants. Similarly, previous studies conducted in male adolescent football players report similar findings for sprint time over a 20 m (Gastin, Bennett and Cook, 2013; Fernández-Galván *et al.*, 2021) and 15 m distance (McCunn *et al.*, 2017) with biologically more mature players (using the Mirwald equation to determine Y-PHV) being faster. Additionally, adolescent females are reported to have a significant decrease in 30 m sprint time as BM and pubertal development occur (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Emmonds *et al.*, 2020). However when comparing changes in sprint time over the 9-month period for all players, 30 m sprint time had no statistical significance. Sprint time is shown to decrease overall as players get older (Datson *et al.*, 2022). The lack of improvement may in part be explained by the change in temperature at the six and nine-month timepoints. Due to the time of year in which outdoor testing occurred (in the winter months) at the six- and nine-month timepoints, temperatures overall were cooler for all teams when compared to the baseline timepoint. Colder temperatures can be seen to impact sprint performance resulting in a decreased sprint time (Carling, Dupont and Le Gall, 2011; Morgans *et al.*, 2023), although there was no significant difference in temperature at any timepoint, the decrease in sprint time observed may have been impacted by a temperature drop. More research would need to be conducted to draw a more concise conclusion of the impact of temperature.

Reference values for physical characteristics of power, speed and aerobic capacity in English female football players have been reported (Datson *et al.*, 2022). These values agree with the current study

suggesting as players get older their sprint time decreases. However, the results from Datson *et al.* (2022) study are based on players chronological age and not biological age or maturity and therefore, can provide variability when comparing results to this data. As age cut-offs for football teams generally are based on chronological age instead of pubertal development, this causes players at different stages of their pubertal development to be grouped within the same team. The observations from this current study and supporting previous studies suggests players within the same team and who are further through their biological and pubertal development could possess performance advantages and therefore selection advantages ahead of their later maturing peers due to the key physical attributes of speed needed within the sport (Gastin, Bennett and Cook, 2013; McCunn *et al.*, 2017; Emmonds *et al.*, 2020).

Countermovement jump performance was greater in players who were biologically more mature and pubertally more mature than their less mature counterparts when assessing the relationship between Y-PHV and CMJ height, at timepoints A and C. At timepoint B, pubertal development and BM had the opposite effect with decreased CMJ height in post-pubertal players compared to their less biologically developed counterparts. This suggests biological maturation may have some effect on metrics of power over a longer time period yet, similar to other studies conducted in female adolescents, the findings are inconclusive (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Ramos *et al.*, 2021; Almeida-Neto *et al.*, 2022). Rapid changes in muscular power are said to occur between the pre-pubertal age of 5 to 10 years, with a secondary spurt occurring around the onset of puberty in females (aged 9-12) (Ford *et al.*, 2011; Ramos *et al.*, 2021). This increase in muscular power could account for the increase in jump height performance at timepoint B. Additionally, a reduction in jump height performance in post-PHV players at timepoint B could be a result of changes or differences to training programmes within or between different teams which could result in pre-PHV players performing better (Ramos *et al.*, 2021). No significant changes in peak power were reported in female football players, with the majority of differences seen at -0.5 – 0.5 Y-PHV (Emmonds *et al.*, 2020). Contrary to this, an increase in biological maturity had a positive relationship on CMJ height, with fully developed female (Ramos *et al.*, 2021) and male (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Fernández-Galván *et al.*, 2021) players performing better than their developing peers. The improvements in these studies could be a result of power and plyometrics training programmes which positively impact jump height performance (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Fernández-Galván *et al.*, 2021; Ramos *et al.*, 2021). Altogether, the results from this study and previous studies assessing lower body power and jump height performance are inconsistent and further research should be conducted to gain a greater understanding of any effects which may be a result of changes in BM such as changes in body composition, CMJ technique or previous

familiarisation/training within different teams/age groups (Sánchez-Sixto, Harrison and Floría, 2018; Ramirez-Campillo *et al.*, 2022).

From the present study, results showed participants who were further through PHV had an increased aerobic capacity, however, when assessing the impact of pubertal development on aerobic capacity no statistical significance was reported. In male adolescents, early maturing players are more likely to have an increased aerobic capacity than later maturing males (Hebestreit *et al.*, 2008). Individuals with higher levels of testosterone are said to develop greater aerobic capabilities during growth and development with results in swimmers suggesting males aerobic capacity enhances following puberty, whilst females remain more constant (Costa *et al.*, 2021; Almeida-Neto *et al.*, 2022). However, the effect of aerobic capacity BM of female adolescents may differ. Similarly to sprint time, temperature could have impacted aerobic performance during the winter months of data collection (timepoints B and C). Colder temperatures of ≤ 5 °C can result in decreased aerobic capacity due to a decrease in muscle temperature reducing muscle efficiency (Carling, Dupont and Le Gall, 2011; Morgans *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, the changes in aerobic performance seen in this study during timepoints B and C may be due to temperature changes. Consequently, more research into longitudinal tracking of female footballer players must be conducted to fully understand the impact BM and pubertal development have on performance metrics of aerobic capacity.

Finally, single-leg knee valgus although having a small decrease in relation to an increased Y-PHV, showed no overall significant differences in relation to BM or pubertal development over the 9-month period. These results differ from data collected in multi-sport adolescents completing SL squats, with the study concluding pre-pubertal adolescents had the greatest knee valgus scores than their developed counterparts (Agrega *et al.*, 2017). This contradicts with other research suggesting more biologically developed females have greater knee valgus during jump landings (Hewett *et al.*, 2015; Westbrook *et al.*, 2020) and females having a larger knee displacement than their male counterparts around BM (Ellenberger *et al.*, 2020). This shows variability in the field and suggests more in-depth research should be conducted in this area to draw more accurate conclusions on the impact of knee valgus on single leg squat movements in adolescents. Validation results (in Chapter 3) question the validity of the HumanTrak system which could make it difficult to draw upon the knee varus/valgus results in this current study and suggests further research is required to understand the effects of BM on knee varus/valgus through the use of a marker-based system.

The present study is not without limitations. Due to the large sample size in data collection and longitudinal nature of the study and the community aspect of the football academy, participants who had missing maturity offset data were removed for statistical analysis purposes due to being unable

to understand the effects of BM on performance metrics. In addition, as a result of the perceived delicate and sensitive personal nature of the self-reporting PDS, completion of the questionnaire was low. A greater uptake in the self-report PDS would have allowed for comparison across smaller PDS groups instead of grouping stages into P2-P3 and P4-P5 (pre-menarche and post-menarche), allowing for deeper analysis to be conducted into the effects each stage of pubertal development may have on performance metrics. A further limitation of the study was the use of the Mirwald predictive equation to assess maturity. It is noted the further to/from-PHV an individual is, the less valid and reliable the Mirwald method is at measuring BM (Cossio-Bolaños *et al.*, 2021; de Almeida-Neto *et al.*, 2022). Although not the most accurate method to measure maturity offset data, due to the large-scale collection of data and the inability to access biological parents height, the Mirwald equation was the most feasible option for data collection (King *et al.*, 2022a; Lüdin *et al.*, 2022). Along with collecting maturation data, collecting body composition of players could have provided greater insight to the study findings, however, after careful consideration this was not included in the present study due to guidance stating body composition should not be completed in anyone under the age of eighteen unless medically indicated by healthcare professionals and has regular monitoring and follow-ups (Ackerman *et al.*, 2020; Mathisen *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, results of knee varus/valgus obtained by HumanTrak should be treated with caution due to the lack of accuracy reported within Chapter 3 of this study and the unknown success of the familiarisation session completed before testing began. When assessing the validity of the HumanTrak system against the 'gold standard' Vicon system the results reported a high variability during overhead and single leg squatting exercises. Knee varus/valgus data should also be split by dominant and non-dominant limbs as opposed to left and right in future research to assess for any changes in performance variables which could be impacted by BM. Participants were familiar with all testing metrics within this study due to completing many previous testing sessions as part of the clubs profiling battery, however a potential learning effect cannot be discounted. Finally, the inability to standardise temperature within the current study poses a limitation due to the unknown effect this may have had on performance metrics, however, due to practical considerations of working in the field and accessing players, data collection needed to be completed at the facilities where the players trained. Future studies should account for this and should aim to conduct well-controlled testing which has a standardised temperature and humidity to reduce the external variable. Due to the cost, player practicalities and large-scale data collection of this study, this would not have been possible.

4.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, performance metrics of lower body power and speed are affected by biological maturation with increased jump height and reduced sprint time seen in more mature players who are

past PHV compared to less mature players. Additional data collection for measures of aerobic capacity should be conducted with a greater number of players pre-PHV to gain a greater understanding of the effects which biological maturation may have on this performance metric. Further research should be undertaken to understand, in more detail, the effects biological maturation could have on performance when splitting the participants into smaller age brackets. This would allow practitioners to understand, in greater depth, where fluctuations in performance may occur and at what stage greatest changes in performance metrics can be seen in relation to BM. The findings from this study can support practitioners' understanding of the fluctuations which may occur during BM to support athlete development and can provide coaches with awareness of these fluctuations when addressing player performance and talent identification.

Chapter 5: General Discussion

When assessing BM, research have favoured the investigation into males, with lacking knowledge and understanding of the effects of BM within females (Peña-González *et al.*, 2018; Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Radnor *et al.*, 2021). Biological maturation has a significant effect on sprint time in female football players, with more biologically mature players reporting faster sprint times than less mature players. These results reflect the findings of previous literature, across both male and female footballers (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Gastin, Bennett and Cook, 2013; McCunn *et al.*, 2017; Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Fernández-Galván *et al.*, 2021; Datson *et al.*, 2022) suggesting biological maturity and individuals' physical characteristics can effect sprint time. Biological maturation had a positive relationship on CMJ height at baseline and nine-months, however there was no statistical significance at the six-month timepoint. This provides a general consensus of increased jump height is evident in biologically more mature individuals however fluctuations in jump height can occur close to when PHV may occur (Malina *et al.*, 2004; Emmonds *et al.*, 2020; Fernández-Galván *et al.*, 2021; Ramos *et al.*, 2021; Almeida-Neto *et al.*, 2022). Jump height was assessed and recorded using the HumanTrak system within this study. To date there are no studies assessing the validity of jump height performance using HumanTrak and therefore could suggest variability in the results obtained compared to previous studies assessing jump height performance. With this being said, marker-less cameras to assess jump height performance, including the Microsoft Kinect (used within HumanTrak) have been previously validated as an accurate measure of jump height performance (McPherson *et al.*, 2017; Mauntel *et al.*, 2021; Webering, Blume and Allaham, 2021).

Maximal aerobic speed assessments had a reduced participant pool due to age restrictions within chapter four of the current thesis and therefore results from this performance metric are limited with only timepoint C reporting a positive correlation between aerobic capacity and BM. Previous research in male adolescents are in agreement with the results from this study as aerobic capacity is suggested to increase with BM (Mota *et al.*, 2002; Mujika *et al.*, 2009; Haugen *et al.*, 2014; Emmonds *et al.*, 2018, 2020; Datson *et al.*, 2020). Future research should adapt and develop methods of assessing aerobic capacity of pre-PHV participants to gain a greater understanding of the effects BM may have on this performance metric.

Biological maturation had no impact on SL squat knee valgus within Chapter 4 of this current thesis. This is pertinent, as results from previous research suggest in both males and females, pre-PHV adolescents have a greater knee valgus during SL squatting movements (Agesta *et al.*, 2017). However, in contrast females post-PHV have also been shown to have a larger knee valgus following jump landings compared to pre- and circa-PHV (Hewett *et al.*, 2015; Westbrook *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, leaving a gap in the literature for future research to be conducted on further assessing the effects of BM on SL knee valgus during SL movements and during jump landings. However, with results from Chapter 3 should be treated with caution, HumanTrak is suggested to be an invalid tool to measure knee valgus during a SL squat with results showing inconsistencies against the gold standard method of assessing movement patterns, Vicon. This suggests the results obtained when measuring SL knee valgus against BM (Chapter 4) may have been impacted by the validity of this HumanTrak system. Future research to assess squat depth and peak knee flexion against BM could be conducted with HumanTrak and would provide valid and accurate results, as the system has similar results to that of the Vicon camera-based system.

Longitudinally, BM had no statistical changes on performance metrics across all three timepoint. All performance variables reported small increases in performance over a nine-month period, however none were statistically significant. This could be a result of the sample size and reduced participant uptake, specifically around the years where PHV may occur. Additionally, no statistical significance over the nine-month period could be a result of the large variability in the standard deviations of performance metrics obtained or other external factors which could have influences the player and impacted the results, for example, a longer day at school with physical education, timing of their last meal, travel times to attend the testing session. Further research with longitudinal tracking of performance with respect to BM should try and account for these external variable and control as many as possible. Research should also be conducted with either a larger sample size or a limited sample of participants who are closer to/from-PHV to gain more understanding of the effects which may occur around this time. A larger sample of participants could give a better understanding of the large-scale changes in performance which may occur as a result of BM and allow for a representation of the longer-term changes which could occur due to BM. Contrary, a smaller sample size limited to players, for example -0.5 to 0.5 Y-PHV, could provide insight into the effects of BM on performance metrics in greater detail to help support the development of athletes around this period of change.

5.1 Limitations and Future Recommendations

A potential limitation when conducting Chapter 3 was the use of the Plug-In Gait model pipeline. This pipeline is a more basic output model used when assessing movements and is not as reliable as other outputs at measuring lower body dynamic movements such as the squat, due to its main purpose being to measure gait analysis (Baker *et al.*, 2017; Leboeuf *et al.*, 2019). Due to the simplicity of the HumanTrak 2D camera system, the use of the Plug-In Gait model allowed a simplified analysis to be used in order to compare results and validate the use of the equipment. Future research should consider isolating the participants lower limbs by using a local coordinate system to allow for comparison of knee angle between the femur and tibia. Using a local coordinate system would allow

for analysis to be conducted removing any changes in results which could be produced by rotation of the hip joint which can occur during a squatting movement (Li *et al.*, 2021). Research of HumanTrak system during fixed lower body ROM exercises should be completed to further validate the systems use as participants knee flexion should remain consistent and can report any variation with the ability to also assess for varus/valgus. Future research should aim to validate the use of the HumanTrak system in relation to more dynamic movements assessing jump height within the countermovement jump, as to our knowledge, there is no research validating the use of the HumanTrak system to collect jump height data.

Additionally, the method used to analyse maturity status in Chapter 4 can become less accurate the further from the age at which PHV occurs for an individual, with most accurate results ranging from -1 to +1 Y-PHV (Cossio-Bolaños *et al.*, 2021; Malina *et al.*, 2021; de Almeida-Neto *et al.*, 2022). If repeating this study, capping the limit of years to- and from-PHV would be recommended to streamline results. Finally, due to poor participant attendance, an increase in participants for Chapter 4 could have allowed for a greater comparison to be reported, especially during the period where the largest changes in PHV occur. The lack of participants, particularly around the age of PHV reduced the ability to split the participants into smaller groupings, of both PHV and pubertal development, therefore removing the opportunity to potentially pin-point where changes could occur during the longitudinal tracking of PHV. This, along with capping the Y-PHV range when assessing maturity status may provide practitioners with more direct and accurate results. The results could provide the possibility to showcase changes or fluctuations which may occur over smaller time periods rather than the changes over the longer nine-month time periods reported within this study. Thus, illustrating possible patterns or irregularities for performance metrics which may occur for individuals developing through PHV and providing female-specific data to support the developmental planning of progress throughout their adolescences in sport.

5.2 Practical Applications

Further research should be conducted on knee flexion and varus/valgus during squatting exercises and additional lower body movements, such as a lunge or countermovement jump, to evaluate the validity of the HumanTrak more generally when assessing lower body fundamental and functional movements. The results from undertaking this more in-depth research could potentially validate this system further and allow practitioners to freely use the HumanTrak system out-with a laboratory-based environment to collect data on athletes. Additionally, future research to investigate the inter- and intra-day reliability of the HumanTrak system during lower body movements, specifically, research into knee flexion and valgus, would be beneficial for practitioners. This would support current research published, in both shoulder and hip flexion, measuring inter- and intra-day reliability

(McCarthy *et al.*, 2022, 2023; Andersen *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, this information would provide accurate and adequate feedback on test-retest reliability and could support practitioners using the HumanTrak system over longitudinal periods of athlete assessments.

This thesis aimed to investigate the effects BM may have on performance metrics of female football players and to validate the use of marker-less movement analysis systems within these applied settings. It is hoped the results will educate practitioners into the effects observed throughout both studies, support the use of marker-less systems within the field for variables of knee flexion and encourage practitioners to be mindful of decisions when assessing player development. Finally, results aim to create future research avenues for further investigation into effects of female BM and marker-less systems in applied environments.

Longitudinal tracking of BM could provide practitioners with an overview of the variation in fluctuations which may occur for athletes and help advance and support developmental plans for the athletes to greater succeed in their sport. Alongside supporting developmental needs of the players, the information gained from the advancements in knowledge around maturation will allow medical staff to support players injury prevention and rehabilitation strategies.

The information provided from this chapter and future research into female biological maturation will support and advance practitioners' decision-making in relation to talent identification processes. An increase in practitioners' knowledge of changes, fluctuations or later development which can occur on an individual level during adolescence to help reduce the volume of selection bias which occurs in youth football academies. However, it will also help coaching staff identify talented players within the academy to ensure adequate support and opportunities are in place to give the players the best possible chance to succeed.

5.3 General Conclusion

This thesis aimed to investigate the effects BM has on performance metrics of knee varus/valgus, CMJ height, 30 m sprint time and MAS within adolescent female footballers. In addition, it aimed to further validate the use of HumanTrak marker-less movement analysis systems within the applied field.

These studies support the use of marker-less cameras for assessing human movements of knee flexion within the applied field. However, if practitioners are interested in measures of knee varus/valgus, 3D laboratory-based systems have higher accuracy and validity for assessing these variables. Biological maturation is suggested to have an impact on performance metrics, however, effects of BM longitudinally still requires further data collection in these performance metrics.

Results from this thesis demonstrate the ability to utilise marker-less systems within the applied field to track and analyse human movement of knee flexion for sporting performance to aid practitioners' ability to support and develop athletes' movement patterns, techniques and injury risk or rehabilitation. However, inconsistencies in knee varus/valgus data suggest additional research into the accuracy of this variable is recommended. As BM has shown to have an effect on performance metrics in female football players, knee valgus data collected through HumanTrak remains questionable due to the lack of validity of the system to analyse this variable. Further research, potentially using 3D marker-based or more valid marker-less systems would provide more accurate results on this variable when measuring the effects of BM. Furthermore, BM reported to have no significant effects on performance metrics longitudinally, however changes in performance metrics were evident across the nine-month period. Taken together, BM effects performance metrics within female football players, although the extent of these effects longitudinally is still unknown. Practitioners can utilise the HumanTrak movement analysis system confidently within an applied, field-based setting to track and assess knee flexion during lower-limb functional movements.

6.0 References

- Acevedo, P., Rekabdar, B. and Mousas, C. (2023) 'Optimizing retroreflective marker set for motion capturing props', *Computers & Graphics*, 115, pp. 181–190. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cag.2023.07.021>.
- Ackerman, K.E. *et al.* (2020) '#REDS (Relative Energy Deficiency in Sport): time for a revolution in sports culture and systems to improve athlete health and performance', *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 54(7), pp. 369–370. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2019-101926>.
- Adesida, Y., Papi, E. and McGregor, A.H. (2019) 'Exploring the Role of Wearable Technology in Sport Kinematics and Kinetics: A Systematic Review', *Sensors*, 19(7), p. 1597. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19071597>.
- Agresta, C. *et al.* (2017) 'Single-Leg Squat Performance in Active Adolescents Aged 8–17 Years', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 31(5), p. 1187. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000001617>.
- Ajjampur, S., Shridhar, V. and Shashikala, K.P. (2021) 'Goal Line Technology Using Line axis detection', in *2021 International Conference on Disruptive Technologies for Multi-Disciplinary Research and Applications (CENTCON)*. *2021 International Conference on Disruptive Technologies for Multi-Disciplinary Research and Applications (CENTCON)*, pp. 304–307. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/CENTCON52345.2021.9688324>.
- Albaladejo-Saura, M. *et al.* (2022) 'The Effect of Age, Biological Maturation and Birth Quartile in the Kinanthropometric and Physical Fitness Differences between Male and Female Adolescent Volleyball Players', *Children*, 9(1), p. 58. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/children9010058>.
- Almeida-Neto, P.F. de *et al.* (2021) 'Lean mass and biological maturation as predictors of muscle power and strength performance in young athletes', *PLOS ONE*, 16(7), p. e0254552. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254552>.
- Almeida-Neto, P.F. de *et al.* (2022) 'Influence of Advancing Biological Maturation on Aerobic and Anaerobic Power and on Sport Performance of Junior Rowers: A Longitudinal Study', *Frontiers in Physiology*, 13. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fphys.2022.892966> (Accessed: 30 August 2023).
- de Almeida-Neto, P.F. *et al.* (2022) 'Reliability of biological maturation analyses performed by equations predicting skeletal age and peak height velocity with hand and wrist X-ray results', *American Journal of Human Biology*, 34(9), p. e23775. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajhb.23775>.
- Altmann, S. *et al.* (2019) 'Validity and reliability of speed tests used in soccer: A systematic review', *PLOS ONE*, 14(8), p. e0220982. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0220982>.
- Andersen, J.T. *et al.* (2023) 'A markerless motion capture system can reliably determine peak trunk flexion while squatting with and without a weighted vest', *Journal of Biomechanics*, 152, p. 111587. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2023.111587>.
- Ansdell, P. *et al.* (2020) 'Physiological sex differences affect the integrative response to exercise: acute and chronic implications', *Experimental Physiology*, 105(12), pp. 2007–2021. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1113/EP088548>.

- Arlinkasari, F., Cushing, D.F. and Miller, E. (2023) “Boys play soccer, girls watch on the corner”: Gendered play and spaces in Jakarta public playgrounds’, *Asian Journal of Social Science*, 51(1), pp. 32–42. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajss.2022.06.001>.
- Armstrong, N. and Mechelen, W.V. (2023) *Oxford Textbook of Children’s Sport and Exercise Medicine*. Oxford University Press.
- Asadi, A. *et al.* (2018) ‘The effects of maturation on jumping ability and sprint adaptations to plyometric training in youth soccer players’, *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 36(21), pp. 2405–2411. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2018.1459151>.
- Asadi, F. and Arjmand, N. (2020) ‘Marker-less versus marker-based driven musculoskeletal models of the spine during static load-handling activities’, *Journal of Biomechanics*, 112, p. 110043. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2020.110043>.
- Australian Catholic University and Vald Performance (2021) ‘HumanTrak Validation Case Study’, pp. 1–10.
- Baker, D. and Heaney, N. (2015) ‘Review of the Literature - Normative Data for Maximal Aerobic Speed for field sport athletes’.
- Baker, R. *et al.* (2017) ‘The Conventional Gait Model - Success and limitations’.
- Bakke, D. and Besier, T. (2022) ‘Shape-model scaled gait models can neglect segment markers without consequential change to inverse kinematics results’, *Journal of Biomechanics*, 137, p. 111086. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2022.111086>.
- Barris, S. and Button, C. (2008) ‘A Review of Vision-Based Motion Analysis in Sport’, *Sports Medicine*, 38(12), pp. 1025–1043. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2165/00007256-200838120-00006>.
- Bates, N.A. *et al.* (2017) ‘Inter- And Intra-Rater Reliability Of Performance Measures Collected With A Single-Camera Motion Analysis System’, *International Journal of Sports Physical Therapy*, 12(4), pp. 520–526.
- Baxter-Jones, A.D.G., Thompson, A.M. and Malina, R.M. (2002) ‘Growth and Maturation in Elite Young Female Athletes’, *Sports Medicine and Arthroscopy Review*, 10(1), pp. 42–49.
- Beshara, P. *et al.* (2020a) ‘The Reliability and Validity of Wearable Inertial Sensors Coupled with the Microsoft Kinect to Measure Shoulder Range-of-Motion’, *Sensors*, 20(24), p. 7238. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20247238>.
- Beshara, P. *et al.* (2020b) ‘The Reliability and Validity of Wearable Inertial Sensors Coupled with the Microsoft Kinect to Measure Shoulder Range-of-Motion’, *Sensors*, 20(24), p. 7238. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20247238>.
- Biro, F.M. *et al.* (2001) ‘Impact of timing of pubertal maturation on growth in black and white female adolescents: The National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute Growth and Health Study’, *The Journal of Pediatrics*, 138(5), pp. 636–643. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1067/mpd.2001.114476>.
- Bland, J.M. and Altman, D.G. (1986) ‘Statistical methods for assessing agreement between two methods of clinical measurement’, *Lancet (London, England)*, 1(8476), pp. 307–310.

- Bond, L. *et al.* (2006) 'A comparison of self-reported puberty using the Pubertal Development Scale and the Sexual Maturation Scale in a school-based epidemiologic survey', *Journal of Adolescence*, 29(5), pp. 709–720. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2005.10.001>.
- Bradley, P.S. *et al.* (2014) 'Gender differences in match performance characteristics of soccer players competing in the UEFA Champions League', *Human Movement Science*, 33, pp. 159–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.humov.2013.07.024>.
- Brooks-Gunn, J. and Peterson, A.C. (2013) *Girls at Puberty: Biological and Psychosocial Perspectives*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Brown, T.D., Vescovi, J.D. and VanHeest, J.L. (2004) 'Assessment of Linear Sprinting Performance: A Theoretical Paradigm', *Journal of Sports Science & Medicine*, 3(4), pp. 203–210.
- Brustio, P.R. *et al.* (2022) 'Small Relative Age Effect Appears in Professional Female Italian Team Sports', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(1), p. 385. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19010385>.
- Bunker, R. and Susnjak, T. (2022) 'The Application of Machine Learning Techniques for Predicting Match Results in Team Sport: A Review', *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 73, pp. 1285–1322. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1613/jair.1.13509>.
- Cable, J.K. and Grider, M.H. (2023) 'physiology, Progesterone', *StatPearls* [Preprint].
- Caldbeck, P. and Dos'Santos, T. (2022) 'A classification of specific movement skills and patterns during sprinting in English Premier League soccer', *PLOS ONE*, 17(11), p. e0277326. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0277326>.
- Camargo, J. *et al.* (2020) 'Automated gap-filling for marker-based biomechanical motion capture data', *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering*, 23(15), pp. 1180–1189. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10255842.2020.1789971>.
- Capranica, L. *et al.* (2013) 'The Gender Gap in Sport Performance: Equity Influences Equality', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 8, pp. 99–103. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.8.1.99>.
- Carling, C., Dupont, G. and Le Gall, F. (2011) 'The Effect of a Cold Environment on Physical Activity Profiles in Elite Soccer Match-Play', *International Journal of Sports Medicine*, 32(07), pp. 542–545. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0031-1273711>.
- Carskadon, M.A. and Acebo, C. (1993) 'A self-administered rating scale for pubertal development', *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 14(3), pp. 190–195. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/1054-139X\(93\)90004-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/1054-139X(93)90004-9).
- Castagna, C. and Castellini, E. (2013) 'Vertical Jump Performance in Italian Male and Female National Team Soccer Players', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 27(4), p. 1156. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0b013e3182610999>.
- Chandrasekar, R. *et al.* (2020) 'Development and validation of a formula for objective assessment of cervical vertebral bone age', *Progress in Orthodontics*, 21(1), p. 38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40510-020-00338-0>.

Chidambaram, S. *et al.* (2022) 'Using Artificial Intelligence-Enhanced Sensing and Wearable Technology in Sports Medicine and Performance Optimisation', *Sensors*, 22(18), p. 6920. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22186920>.

Chimera, N.J., Smith, C.A. and Warren, M. (2015) 'Injury History, Sex, and Performance on the Functional Movement Screen and Y Balance Test', *Journal of Athletic Training*, 50(5), pp. 475–485. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4085/1062-6050-49.6.02>.

Choo, C.Z.Y., Chow, J.Y. and Komar, J. (2022) 'Validation of the Perception Neuron system for full-body motion capture', *PLOS ONE*, 17(1), p. e0262730. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0262730>.

Claudino, J.G. *et al.* (2019) 'Current Approaches to the Use of Artificial Intelligence for Injury Risk Assessment and Performance Prediction in Team Sports: a Systematic Review', *Sports Medicine - Open*, 5(1), p. 28. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40798-019-0202-3>.

Cobley, S. *et al.* (2009) 'Annual Age-Grouping and Athlete Development', *Sports Medicine*, 39(3), pp. 235–256. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2165/00007256-200939030-00005>.

Cole, T.J. (2012) 'The development of growth references and growth charts', *Annals of Human Biology*, 39(5), pp. 382–394. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/03014460.2012.694475>.

Collins, T.D. *et al.* (2009) 'A six degrees-of-freedom marker set for gait analysis: Repeatability and comparison with a modified Helen Hayes set', *Gait & Posture*, 30(2), pp. 173–180. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2009.04.004>.

Colyer, S.L. *et al.* (2018) 'A Review of the Evolution of Vision-Based Motion Analysis and the Integration of Advanced Computer Vision Methods Towards Developing a Markerless System', *Sports Medicine - Open*, 4(1), p. 24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40798-018-0139-y>.

Cook, G. *et al.* (2014a) 'Functional Movement Screening: The Use Of Fundamental Movements As An Assessment Of Function - Part 1', *International Journal of Sports Physical Therapy*, 9(3), pp. 396–409.

Cook, G. *et al.* (2014b) 'Functional Movement Screening: The Use Of Fundamental Movements As An Assessment Of Function - Part 1', *International Journal of Sports Physical Therapy*, 9(3), pp. 396–409.

Cook, G., Burton, L. and Hoogenboom, B. (2006) 'Pre-Participation Screening: The Use of Fundamental Movements as an Assessment of Function – Part 1', *North American Journal of Sports Physical Therapy : NAJSPT*, 1(2), pp. 62–72.

Cossio-Bolaños, M. *et al.* (2021) 'Equations predicting maturity status: Validation in a cross-sectional sample to assess physical growth and body adiposity in Chilean children and adolescents', *Endocrinología, Diabetes y Nutrición (English ed.)*, 68(10), pp. 689–698. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.endien.2021.11.033>.

Costa, T. *et al.* (2021) 'Influence of Biological Maturity on the Muscular Strength of Young Male and Female Swimmers', *Journal of Human Kinetics*, 78(1), pp. 67–77. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2478/hukin-2021-0029>.

Costello, J.T., Bieuzen, F. and Bleakley, C.M. (2014) 'Where are all the female participants in Sports and Exercise Medicine research?', *European Journal of Sport Science*, 14(8), pp. 847–851. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461391.2014.911354>.

Cowley, E.S. *et al.* (2021) ‘“Invisible Sportswomen”: The Sex Data Gap in Sport and Exercise Science Research’, *Women in Sport & Physical Activity Journal*, 29(2), pp. 146–151.

Cumming, S. *et al.* (2018) ‘Biological maturation, relative age and self-regulation in male professional academy soccer players: A test of the underdog hypothesis’, *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 39. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2018.08.007>.

Datson, N. *et al.* (2020) ‘High-intensity endurance capacity assessment as a tool for talent identification in elite youth female soccer’, *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 38(11–12), pp. 1313–1319. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2019.1656323>.

Datson, N. *et al.* (2022) ‘Reference values for performance test outcomes relevant to English female soccer players’, *Science and Medicine in Football*, 6(5), pp. 589–596. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2022.2037156>.

Davidson, R. *et al.* (2022) *Sport and Exercise Physiology Testing Guidelines: Volume II - Exercise and Clinical Testing*. Fifth. Routledge.

De Tobel, J. *et al.* (2017) ‘An automated technique to stage lower third molar development on panoramic radiographs for age estimation: a pilot study.’, *The Journal of Forensic Odontostomatology*, 35(2), pp. 42–54.

Demirjian, A., Goldstein, H. and Tanner, J.M. (1973) ‘A New System of Dental Age Assessment’, *Human Biology*, 45(2), pp. 211–227.

Deprez, D. *et al.* (2013) ‘Relative Age, Biological Maturation and Anaerobic Characteristics in Elite Youth Soccer Players’, *International Journal of Sports Medicine*, 34(10), pp. 897–903. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0032-1333262>.

Di Renzo, G.C., Tosto, V. and Tsibizova, V. (2020) ‘Progesterone: History, facts, and artifacts’, *Best Practice & Research Clinical Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 69, pp. 2–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2020.07.012>.

Dirksen, R.L. (2022) ‘Development of a new ultrasound device for determining maturity based on bone age assessment’.

Edwards, T. *et al.* (2021) ‘Influence of age and maturation status on sprint acceleration characteristics in junior Australian football’, *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 39(14), pp. 1585–1593. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2021.1886699>.

Eisenmann, J.C., Till, K. and Baker, J. (2020) ‘Growth, maturation and youth sports: issues and practical solutions’, *Annals of Human Biology*, 47(4), pp. 324–327. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03014460.2020.1764099>.

Ellenberger, L. *et al.* (2020) ‘Dynamic knee valgus in competitive alpine skiers: Observation from youth to elite and influence of biological maturation’, *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 30(7), pp. 1212–1220. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.13657>.

Elliott-Sale, K.J. *et al.* (2021) ‘Methodological Considerations for Studies in Sport and Exercise Science with Women as Participants: A Working Guide for Standards of Practice for Research on Women’, *Sports Medicine*, 51(5), pp. 843–861. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-021-01435-8>.

Elphinston, J. (2008) *Stability, Sport and Performance Movement: Great Technique without Injury*. 1st edn.

Eltoukhy, M. *et al.* (2016) 'Validation of the Microsoft Kinect® camera system for measurement of lower extremity jump landing and squatting kinematics', *Sports Biomechanics*, 15(1), pp. 89–102. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14763141.2015.1123766>.

Emmanuel, M. and Bokor, B.R. (2017) 'Tanner Stages', *StatPearls* [Preprint].

Emmonds, S. *et al.* (2018) 'Influence of age on the anthropometric and performance characteristics of high-level youth female soccer players', *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 13(5), pp. 779–786. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1747954118757437>.

Emmonds, S. *et al.* (2020) 'Physical Characteristics of Elite Youth Female Soccer Players Characterized by Maturity Status', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 34(8), pp. 2321–2328. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000002795>.

Emmonds, S., Heyward, O. and Jones, B. (2019) 'The Challenge of Applying and Undertaking Research in Female Sport', *Sports Medicine - Open*, 5(1), p. 51. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40798-019-0224-x>.

Esan, T.A., Yengopal, V. and Schepartz, L.A. (2017) 'The Demirjian versus the Willems method for dental age estimation in different populations: A meta-analysis of published studies', *PLOS ONE*, 12(11), p. e0186682. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186682>.

Eskandarifard, E. *et al.* (2022) 'Exploring interactions between maturity status and playing time with fluctuations in physical fitness and hormonal markers in youth soccer players', *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), p. 4463. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-08567-5>.

Fernández-Galván, L.M. *et al.* (2021) 'Examination of the Sprinting and Jumping Force-Velocity Profiles in Young Soccer Players at Different Maturational Stages', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(9), p. 4646. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18094646>.

Ford, P. *et al.* (2011) 'The Long-Term Athlete Development model: Physiological evidence and application', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 29(4), pp. 389–402. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2010.536849>.

Fransen, J. *et al.* (2018) 'Improving the Prediction of Maturity From Anthropometric Variables Using a Maturity Ratio', *Pediatric Exercise Science*, 30(2), pp. 296–307. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.2017-0009>.

Fransen, J., Skorski, S. and Baxter-Jones, A.D.G. (2021) 'Estimating is not measuring: the use of non-invasive estimations of somatic maturity in youth football', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 5(4), pp. 261–262. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2021.1975808>.

Frevel, N., Beiderbeck, D. and Schmidt, S.L. (2022) 'The impact of technology on sports – A prospective study', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 182, p. 121838. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121838>.

Garcia, C. *et al.* (2018) 'Health-related quality of life of Portuguese children and adolescents according to their biological maturation and volume of physical activity', *Quality of Life Research*, 27(6), pp. 1483–1492. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-018-1822-7>.

Gastin, P.B., Bennett, G. and Cook, J. (2013) 'Biological maturity influences running performance in junior Australian football', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 16(2), pp. 140–145. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2012.05.005>.

Goldfarb, N. *et al.* (2021) 'Open source Vicon Toolkit for motion capture and Gait Analysis', *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 212, p. 106414. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2021.106414>.

Goncharuk-Khomyn, M. *et al.* (2020) 'Correspondence between dental and skeletal maturity parameters among patients with different sagittal relationships at the end of puberty period'. Available at: <https://dspace.uzhnu.edu.ua/jspui/handle/lib/47199> (Accessed: 24 February 2023).

Griffin, J. *et al.* (2021) 'Contextual factors influencing the characteristics of female football players', *The Journal of Sports Medicine and Physical Fitness*, 61(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.23736/S0022-4707.20.11182-4>.

Guimarães, E. *et al.* (2021) 'The role of growth, maturation and sporting environment on the development of performance and technical and tactical skills in youth basketball players: The INEX study', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 39(9), pp. 979–991. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2020.1853334>.

Guitart, M. *et al.* (2022) 'Use of GPS to measure external load and estimate the incidence of muscle injuries in men's football: A novel descriptive study', *PLOS ONE*, 17(2), p. e0263494. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0263494>.

Hackett, D.A. *et al.* (2023) 'Effects of Age and Sex on Aerobic Fitness, Sprint Performance, and Change of Direction Speed in High School Athletes', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 37(5), p. e325. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000004354>.

Halder, S., Saha, G. and Shaw, C. (2023) 'Impact of Technology on the Sports Field', in, pp. 13–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.9734/bpi/rpst/v3/17711D>.

Harkness-Armstrong, A. *et al.* (2022) 'Determining age-specific velocity thresholds for elite youth female soccer players', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 6(5), pp. 581–588. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2021.1991585>.

Harsted, S. *et al.* (2019) 'Concurrent validity of lower extremity kinematics and jump characteristics captured in pre-school children by a markerless 3D motion capture system', *Chiropractic & Manual Therapies*, 27(1), p. 39. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12998-019-0261-z>.

Haugen, T., Tønnessen, E. and Seiler, S. (2012) 'Speed and Countermovement-Jump Characteristics of Elite Female Soccer Players, 1995-2010', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.7.4.340>.

Haugen, T.A. *et al.* (2014) 'VO₂max Characteristics of Elite Female Soccer Players, 1989–2007', *International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance*, 9(3), pp. 515–521. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.2012-0150>.

Hebestreit, H. *et al.* (eds) (2008) *The young athlete*. Malden, Mass.; Oxford: Blackwell Pub (Encyclopaedia of sports medicine, v. 13).

Heishman, A. *et al.* (2018) 'Counter-movement Jump Reliability Performed With and Without an Arm Swing in NCAA Division 1 Intercollegiate Basketball Players', *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 34, p. 1. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000002812>.

Helsen, W.F., van Winckel, J. and Williams, A.M. (2005) 'The relative age effect in youth soccer across Europe', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 23(6), pp. 629–636. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640410400021310>.

Herman, D.C. *et al.* (2022) 'Effect of Strength Training on Jump-Landing Biomechanics in Adolescent Females', *Sports Health*, 14(1), pp. 69–76. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/19417381211056089>.

Hewett, T.E. *et al.* (2015) 'Longitudinal Increases in Knee Abduction Moments in Females during Adolescent Growth', *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 47(12), pp. 2579–2585. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000000700.H>

Hewett, T.E., Myer, G.D. and Ford, K.R. (2004) 'Decrease in Neuromuscular Control About the Knee with Maturation in Female Athletes', *JBSJ*, 86(8), p. 1601.

Hopkins, W.G. *et al.* (2009) 'Progressive Statistics for Studies in Sports Medicine and Exercise Science', *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, 41(1), pp. 3–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0b013e31818cb278>.

Houck, J., Yack, H.J. and Cuddeford, T. (2004) 'Validity and comparisons of tibiofemoral orientations and displacement using a femoral tracking device during early to mid stance of walking', *Gait & Posture*, 19(1), pp. 76–84. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0966-6362\(03\)00033-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0966-6362(03)00033-X).

Islam, A. *et al.* (2020) 'Stereo Vision-Based 3D Positioning and Tracking', *IEEE Access*, 8, pp. 138771–138787. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3011360>.

Jeras, N.M.J., Bovend'Eerd, T.J.H. and McCrum, C. (2020) 'Biomechanical mechanisms of jumping performance in youth elite female soccer players', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 38(11–12), pp. 1335–1341. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2019.1674526>.

Johnson, D.M. *et al.* (2020) 'Growing pains: Maturity associated variation in injury risk in academy football', *European Journal of Sport Science*, 20(4), pp. 544–552. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461391.2019.1633416>.

Karimi, A. *et al.* (2021) 'Dental age estimation: Development and validation of a reference data set for Kuwaiti children, adolescents, and young adults', *Archives of Oral Biology*, 127, p. 105130. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archoralbio.2021.105130>.

Kerkhoff, A., Wagner, H. and Peikenkamp, K. (2020) 'Comparison of six different marker sets to analyze knee kinematics and kinetics during landings', *Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering*, 6(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/cdbme-2020-2009>.

Khamis, H.J. and Roche, A.F. (1994) 'Predicting Adult Stature Without Using Skeletal Age: The Khamis-Roche Method', *Pediatrics*, 94(4), pp. 504–507. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.94.4.504>.

Kim, K.-W. and Lim, B.-O. (2014) 'Effects of menarcheal age on the anterior cruciate ligament injury risk factors during single-legged drop landing in female artistic elite gymnasts', *Archives of Orthopaedic and Trauma Surgery*, 134(11), pp. 1565–1571. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00402-014-2055-z>.

King, M. *et al.* (2022a) 'Initial fitness, maturity status, and total training explain small and inconsistent proportions of the variance in physical development of adolescent footballers across one season', *Research in Sports Medicine*, 30(3), pp. 283–294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15438627.2021.1888106>.

King, M. *et al.* (2022b) 'Initial fitness, maturity status, and total training explain small and inconsistent proportions of the variance in physical development of adolescent footballers across one season', *Research in Sports Medicine*, 30(3), pp. 283–294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15438627.2021.1888106>.

Kırkoğlu, N. (2023) 'Innovative developments in basketball: Utilization of technology', in, pp. 135–150. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.58830/ozgur.pub315.c1484>.

Koopman-Verhoeff, M.E. *et al.* (2020) 'Classifying Pubertal Development Using Child and Parent Report: Comparing the Pubertal Development Scales to Tanner Staging', *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 66(5), pp. 597–602. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2019.11.308>.

Kostas, M. (2022) "'Real" boys, sissies and tomboys: exploring the material-discursive intra-actions of football, bodies, and heteronormative discourses', *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 43(1), pp. 63–83. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2021.1999790>.

Kozieł, S.M. and Malina, R.M. (2018) 'Modified Maturity Offset Prediction Equations: Validation in Independent Longitudinal Samples of Boys and Girls', *Sports Medicine*, 48(1), pp. 221–236. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-017-0750-y>.

Kraus, K. *et al.* (2020) 'Concurrent Validity of 2D and Inertial Goniometer Motion Assessment', *International Journal of Athletic Therapy & Training*, 25(3), pp. 134–139.

Krolo, A. *et al.* (2020) 'Agility Testing in Youth Football (Soccer) Players; Evaluating Reliability, Validity, and Correlates of Newly Developed Testing Protocols', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(1), p. 294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17010294>.

van der Kruk, E. and Reijne, M.M. (2018) 'Accuracy of human motion capture systems for sport applications; state-of-the-art review', *European Journal of Sport Science*, 18(6), pp. 806–819. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461391.2018.1463397>.

Leboeuf, F. *et al.* (2019) 'The conventional gait model, an open-source implementation that reproduces the past but prepares for the future', *Gait & Posture*, 69, pp. 235–241. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2019.04.015>.

Leone, M. and Comtois, A.S. (2007) 'Validity and reliability of self-assessment of sexual maturity in elite adolescent athletes', *The Journal of sports medicine and physical fitness*, 47, pp. 361–5.

Li, B. and Xu, X. (2021) 'Application of Artificial Intelligence in Basketball Sport', *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*, 11(7), pp. 54–67. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.12775/JEHS.2021.11.07.005>.

Li, X. *et al.* (2021) 'Novice Female Exercisers Exhibited Different Biomechanical Loading Profiles during Full-Squat and Half-Squat Practice', *Biology*, 10(11), p. 1184. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology10111184>.

Lloyd, R.S. *et al.* (2014) 'Chronological Age vs. Biological Maturation: Implications for Exercise Programming in Youth', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 28(5), pp. 1454–1464. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000000391>.

Lloyd, R.S. *et al.* (2015) 'Relationships between functional movement screen scores, maturation and physical performance in young soccer players', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 33(1), pp. 11–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2014.918642>.

Lloyd, R.S. and Oliver, J.L. (2012a) 'The Youth Physical Development Model: A New Approach to Long-Term Athletic Development', *Strength & Conditioning Journal*, 34(3), pp. 61–72. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/SSC.0b013e31825760ea>.

Lloyd, R.S. and Oliver, J.L. (2012b) 'The Youth Physical Development Model: A New Approach to Long-Term Athletic Development', *Strength & Conditioning Journal*, 34(3), pp. 61–72. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/SSC.0b013e31825760ea>.

Lopes, T.J.A. *et al.* (2018) 'Reliability and Validity of Frontal Plane Kinematics of the Trunk and Lower Extremity Measured With 2-Dimensional Cameras During Athletic Tasks: A Systematic Review With Meta-analysis', *Journal of Orthopaedic & Sports Physical Therapy*, 48(10), pp. 812–822. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2519/jospt.2018.8006>.

Lüdin, D. *et al.* (2022) 'Effect of bio-banding on physiological and technical-tactical key performance indicators in youth elite soccer', *European Journal of Sport Science*, 22(11), pp. 1659–1667. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461391.2021.1974100>.

Lundquist, M. *et al.* (2021a) 'Set distance time trials for predicting maximal aerobic speed in female Australian Rules Footballers', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 24(4), pp. 391–396. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2020.10.002>.

Lundquist, M. *et al.* (2021b) 'Set distance time trials for predicting maximal aerobic speed in female Australian Rules Footballers', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 24(4), pp. 391–396. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2020.10.002>.

Luo, J., Gao, W. and Wang, Z.L. (2021) 'The Triboelectric Nanogenerator as an Innovative Technology toward Intelligent Sports', *Advanced Materials*, 33(17), p. 2004178. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202004178>.

MacMaster, C. *et al.* (2021) 'The effect of bio-banding on the anthropometric, physical fitness and functional movement characteristics of academy soccer players', *PLOS ONE*, 16(11), p. e0260136. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0260136>.

Maggi, A. and Della Torre, S. (2018) 'Sex, metabolism and health', *Molecular Metabolism*, 15, pp. 3–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmet.2018.02.012>.

Mainer-Pardos, E. *et al.* (2021) 'Age-related differences in linear sprint in adolescent female soccer players', *BMC Sports Science, Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 13(1), p. 97. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13102-021-00327-8>.

Malina, R. *et al.* (2015a) 'Biological maturation of youth athletes: Assessment and implications', *British journal of sports medicine*, 49, pp. 852–859. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2015-094623>.

Malina, R. *et al.* (2015b) 'Biological maturation of youth athletes: Assessment and implications', *British journal of sports medicine*, 49, pp. 852–859. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2015-094623>.

Malina, R.M. *et al.* (2004) 'Maturity-associated variation in the growth and functional capacities of youth football (soccer) players 13–15 years', *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 91(5), pp. 555–562. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-003-0995-z>.

Malina, R.M. (2011) 'Skeletal Age and Age Verification in Youth Sport', *Sports Medicine*, 41(11), pp. 925–947. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2165/11590300-000000000-00000>.

Malina, R.M. *et al.* (2019) 'Bio-Banding in Youth Sports: Background, Concept, and Application', *Sports Medicine*, 49(11), pp. 1671–1685. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-019-01166-x>.

Malina, R.M. *et al.* (2021) 'Prediction of maturity offset and age at peak height velocity in a longitudinal series of boys and girls', *American Journal of Human Biology*, 33(6), p. e23551. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajhb.23551>.

Malina, R.M., Ackerman, K.E. and Rogol, A.D. (2016) 'Growth and the Young Female Athlete', in C.J. Stein, K.E. Ackerman, and A. Stracciolini (eds) *The Young Female Athlete*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Contemporary Pediatric and Adolescent Sports Medicine), pp. 1–14. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21632-4_1.

Malina, R.M., Bouchard, C. and Bar-Or, O. (2004) *Growth, Maturation, and Physical Activity*. Human Kinetics.

Malina, R.M. and Koziel, S.M. (2014) 'Validation of maturity offset in a longitudinal sample of Polish girls', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 32(14), pp. 1374–1382. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2014.889846>.

Malone, J.J. *et al.* (2017) 'Unpacking the Black Box: Applications and Considerations for Using GPS Devices in Sport', *International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance*, 12(s2), pp. S2-26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.2016-0236>.

Manna, I. (2014) 'Growth Development and Maturity in Children and Adolescent: Relation to Sports and Physical Activity', *American Journal of Sports Science and Medicine*, 2(5A), pp. 48–50. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.12691/ajssm-2-5A-11>.

Manzoor Mughal, A., Hassan, N. and Ahmed, A. (2014) 'Bone Age Assessment Methods: A Critical Review', *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 30(1), pp. 211–215. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.301.4295>.

Marques, V.B. *et al.* (2017) 'The Functional Movement Screen (FMStm) In Elite Young Soccer Players Between 14 And 20 Years: Composite Score, Individual-Test Scores And Asymmetries', *International Journal of Sports Physical Therapy*, 12(6), pp. 977–985.

Marshall, W.A. and Tanner, J.M. (1969) 'Variations in pattern of pubertal changes in girls.', *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, 44(235), pp. 291–303.

Martínez-García, M.-L. and Rodríguez-Menéndez, C. (2020) "'I can try it": negotiating masculinity through football in the playground', *Sport, Education and Society*, 25(2), pp. 199–212. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2018.1564653>.

Martínez-Lagunas, V., Niessen, M. and Hartmann, U. (2014) 'Women's football: Player characteristics and demands of the game', *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 3(4), pp. 258–272. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2014.10.001>.

Martín-Moya, R. *et al.* (2023) 'Differences and relationship in functional movement screen (FMS™) scores and physical fitness in males and female semi-professional soccer players', *PeerJ*, 11, p. e16649. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.16649>.

Mathisen, T.F. *et al.* (2023) 'Best practice recommendations for body composition considerations in sport to reduce health and performance risks: a critical review, original survey and expert opinion by a subgroup of the IOC consensus on Relative Energy Deficiency in Sport (REDs)', *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 57(17), pp. 1148–1160. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2023-106812>.

Mauntel, T.C. *et al.* (2021) 'Validation of a Commercially Available Markerless Motion-Capture System for Trunk and Lower Extremity Kinematics During a Jump-Landing Assessment', *Journal of Athletic Training*, 56(2), pp. 177–190. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4085/1062-6050-0023.20>.

Maykut, J.N. *et al.* (2015) 'Concurrent Validity And Reliability Of 2D Kinematic Analysis Of Frontal Plane Motion During Running', *International Journal of Sports Physical Therapy*, 10(2), pp. 136–146.

McCall, A. *et al.* (2014) 'Risk factors, testing and preventative strategies for non-contact injuries in professional football: current perceptions and practices of 44 teams from various premier leagues', *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 48(18), pp. 1352–1357. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2014-093439>.

McCarthy, A. *et al.* (2022) 'Examining The Intra- And Inter-Day Reliability Of The Vald Humantrak For Range Of Motion Of The Shoulder In Fixed- And Free-Range Conditions'.

McCarthy, A. *et al.* (2023) 'Evaluating the intra- and inter-day reliability of output measures for the VALD HumanTrak: dynamic movements and range of motion of the shoulder and hip with body armour', *Ergonomics*, 66(3), pp. 406–418. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139.2022.2092218>.

McCosker, C. *et al.* (2022) 'Principles for technology use in athlete support across the skill level continuum', *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 17(2), pp. 437–444. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/174795412111033471>.

McCunn, R. *et al.* (2016) 'Reliability and Association with Injury of Movement Screens: A Critical Review', *Sports Medicine*, 46(6), pp. 763–781. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-015-0453-1>.

McCunn, R. *et al.* (2017) 'Influence of Physical Maturity Status on Sprinting Speed Among Youth Soccer Players', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 31(7), p. 1795. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000001654>.

McFadden, B.A. *et al.* (2020) 'Comparison of Internal and External Training Loads in Male and Female Collegiate Soccer Players During Practices vs. Games', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 34(4), p. 969. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000003485>.

McKeown, I. *et al.* (2014) 'Athletic Ability Assessment: A Movement Assessment Protocol For Athletes', *International Journal of Sports Physical Therapy*, 9(7), pp. 862–873.

McPherson, A.L. *et al.* (2017) 'Validity Of Athletic Task Performance Measures Collected With A Single-Camera Motion Analysis System As Compared To Standard Clinical Measurements', *International Journal of Sports Physical Therapy*, 12(4), pp. 527–634.

Mendez-Villanueva, A. *et al.* (2011) 'Age-related differences in acceleration, maximum running speed, and repeated-sprint performance in young soccer players', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 29(5), pp. 477–484. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2010.536248>.

Mendle, J. *et al.* (2019) 'Understanding Puberty and Its Measurement: Ideas for Research in a New Generation', *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 29(1), pp. 82–95. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jora.12371>.

Menolotto, M. *et al.* (2020) 'Motion Capture Technology in Industrial Applications: A Systematic Review', *Sensors*, 20(19), p. 5687. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20195687>.

Mentiplay, B.F. *et al.* (2015) 'Gait assessment using the Microsoft Xbox One Kinect: Concurrent validity and inter-day reliability of spatiotemporal and kinematic variables', *Journal of Biomechanics*, 48(10), pp. 2166–2170. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2015.05.021>.

Metcalf, C.D. *et al.* (2013) 'Markerless Motion Capture and Measurement of Hand Kinematics: Validation and Application to Home-Based Upper Limb Rehabilitation', *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 60(8), pp. 2184–2192. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2013.2250286>.

Michailidis, Y., Metaxas, T. and Moutsanos, N. (2022) 'The effects of a repeated sprint ability program on youth soccer players' physical performance', *Trends in Sport Sciences 2022 Vol.29 No.2* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://www.wbc.poznan.pl/dlibra/doccontent?id=522957>.

Mills, K. *et al.* (2017) 'What is the most accurate and reliable methodological approach for predicting peak height velocity in adolescents? A systematic review', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 20(6), pp. 572–577. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2016.10.012>.

Mirwald, R.L. *et al.* (2002) 'An Assessment of Maturity from Anthropometric Measurements', *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 34(4), pp. 689–694.

Monaco, J.-T. and Schoenfeld, B.J. (2019) 'A Review of the Current Literature on the Utility of the Functional Movement Screen as a Screening Tool to Identify Athletes' Risk for Injury', *Strength & Conditioning Journal*, 41(5), p. 17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/SSC.0000000000000481>.

Morgans, R. *et al.* (2023) 'The relationship between ambient temperature and match running performance of elite soccer players', *PLOS ONE*, 18(7), p. e0288494. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0288494>.

Mota, J. *et al.* (2002) 'Association of maturation, sex, and body fat in cardiorespiratory fitness', *American Journal of Human Biology*, 14(6), pp. 707–712. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajhb.10086>.

Mujika, I. *et al.* (2009) 'Fitness determinants of success in men's and women's football', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 27(2), pp. 107–114. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640410802428071>.

Mujika, I. and Taipale, R.S. (2019) 'Sport Science on Women, Women in Sport Science', *International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance*, 14(8), pp. 1013–1014. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.2019-0514>.

Müller, L. *et al.* (2015) '[The assessment of biological maturation for talent selection - which method can be used?]', *Sportverletzung Sportschaden: Organ Der Gesellschaft Fur Orthopadisch-*

Traumatologische Sportmedizin, 29(1), pp. 56–63. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0034-1399043>.

O'Brien, T.D. *et al.* (2009) 'Strong relationships exist between muscle volume, joint power and whole-body external mechanical power in adults and children', *Experimental Physiology*, 94(6), pp. 731–738. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1113/expphysiol.2008.045062>.

O'Brien-Smith, J. *et al.* (2020) 'Same or different? A comparison of anthropometry, physical fitness and perceptual motor characteristics in male and female youth soccer players', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 4(1), pp. 37–44. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2019.1650197>.

Okholm Kryger, K. *et al.* (2022) 'Research on women's football: a scoping review', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 6(5), pp. 549–558. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2020.1868560>.

Ota, M. *et al.* (2020) 'Verification of reliability and validity of motion analysis systems during bilateral squat using human pose tracking algorithm', *Gait & Posture*, 80, pp. 62–67. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2020.05.027>.

Oziegbe, E.O., Esan, T.A. and Oyedele, T.A. (2014) 'Brief communication: Emergence chronology of permanent teeth in Nigerian children', *American Journal of Physical Anthropology*, 153(3), pp. 506–511. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.22447>.

Papla, M. *et al.* (2020) 'Relationships between Linear Sprint, Lower-Body Power Output and Change of Direction Performance in Elite Soccer Players', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(17), p. 6119. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17176119>.

Parr, J., Winwood, K., Hodson-Tole, E., Deconinck, F.J.A., Parry, L., *et al.* (2020) 'Predicting the timing of the peak of the pubertal growth spurt in elite male youth soccer players: evaluation of methods', *Annals of Human Biology*, 47(4), pp. 400–408. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03014460.2020.1782989>.

Parr, J., Winwood, K., Hodson-Tole, E., Deconinck, F.J.A., Hill, J.P., *et al.* (2020) 'The Main and Interactive Effects of Biological Maturity and Relative Age on Physical Performance in Elite Youth Soccer Players', *Journal of Sports Medicine*, 2020, p. e1957636. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/1957636>.

Paszkewicz, J.R., McCarty, C.W. and Van Lunen, B.L. (2013) 'Comparison of Functional and Static Evaluation Tools Among Adolescent Athletes', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 27(10), p. 2842. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0b013e3182815770>.

Păun, D. (2023) 'Game-Changing Innovations: Exploring the Impact of Technology on Football', *Edtech*, 3(1), pp. 24–33.

Pavillon, T. *et al.* (2021) 'Sprint and jump performances in highly trained young soccer players of different chronological age: Effects of linear Vs. Change-Of-Direction sprint training', *Journal of Exercise Science & Fitness*, 19(2), pp. 81–90. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesf.2020.10.003>.

Payton, C.J. and Burden, A. (2018) *Biomechanical Evaluation of Movement in Sport and Exercise*. 2nd edn. Routledge.

Pedersen, A.V., Aksdal, I.M. and Stalsberg, R. (2019) 'Scaling Demands of Soccer According to Anthropometric and Physiological Sex Differences: A Fairer Comparison of Men's and Women's Soccer', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00762>.

Peña-González, I. *et al.* (2018) 'Relative Age Effect, Biological Maturation, and Coaches' Efficacy Expectations in Young Male Soccer Players', *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 89(3), pp. 373–379. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2018.1486003>.

Peña-González, I. *et al.* (2022) 'The maturity status but not the relative age influences elite young football players' physical performance', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 6(3), pp. 309–316. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2022.2053338>.

Petersen, A.C. *et al.* (1988) 'A self-report measure of pubertal status: Reliability, validity, and initial norms', *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 17(2), pp. 117–133. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01537962>.

Pfister, A. *et al.* (2014) 'Comparative abilities of Microsoft Kinect and Vicon 3D motion capture for gait analysis', *Journal of Medical Engineering & Technology*, 38(5), pp. 274–280. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/03091902.2014.909540>.

Philippaerts, R.M. *et al.* (2006) 'The relationship between peak height velocity and physical performance in youth soccer players', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 24(3), pp. 221–230. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640410500189371>.

Pino-Ortega, J. *et al.* (2022a) 'Comparison of the validity and reliability of local positioning systems against other tracking technologies in team sport: A systematic review', *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part P: Journal of Sports Engineering and Technology*, 236(2), pp. 73–82. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754337120988236>.

Pino-Ortega, J. *et al.* (2022b) 'Comparison of the validity and reliability of local positioning systems against other tracking technologies in team sport: A systematic review', *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part P: Journal of Sports Engineering and Technology*, 236(2), pp. 73–82. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754337120988236>.

Poehling, R.A. *et al.* (2021) 'Physical performance development in a female national team soccer program', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 24(6), pp. 597–602. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2020.12.009>.

Portas, M.D. *et al.* (2016) 'Maturational effect on Functional Movement Screen™ score in adolescent soccer players', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 19(10), pp. 854–858. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2015.12.001>.

Prieske, O. *et al.* (2019) 'Effects of Drop Height on Jump Performance in Male and Female Elite Adolescent Handball Players', *International Journal of Sports Physiology & Performance*, 14(5), pp. 674–680.

Pueo Ortega, B. and Jiménez Olmedo, J.M. (2017) 'Application of motion capture technology for sport performance analysis', *Retos: nuevas tendencias en educación física, deporte y recreación*, (32), pp. 241–247.

Pyne, D., Spencer, M. and Mujika, I. (2013) 'Improving the Value of Fitness Testing for Football', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/IJSP.2013-0453>.

Radnor, J.M. *et al.* (2018) 'The Influence of Growth and Maturation on Stretch-Shortening Cycle Function in Youth', *Sports Medicine*, 48(1), pp. 57–71. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-017-0785-0>.

Radnor, J.M. *et al.* (2021) 'Maturity Has a Greater Association than Relative Age with Physical Performance in English Male Academy Soccer Players', *Sports*, 9(12), p. 171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports9120171>.

Raghu, S.L. *et al.* (2019) 'Static accuracy analysis of Vicon T40s motion capture cameras arranged externally for motion capture in constrained aquatic environments', *Journal of Biomechanics*, 89, pp. 139–142. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2019.04.029>.

Rajšp, A. and Fister, I. (2020) 'A Systematic Literature Review of Intelligent Data Analysis Methods for Smart Sport Training', *Applied Sciences*, 10(9), p. 3013. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10093013>.

Ramirez-Campillo, R. *et al.* (2022) 'The effects of plyometric jump training on physical fitness attributes in basketball players: A meta-analysis', *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 11(6), pp. 656–670. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2020.12.005>.

Ramos, G.P. *et al.* (2021) 'Comparison of Physical Fitness and Anthropometrical Profiles Among Brazilian Female Soccer National Teams From U15 to Senior Categories', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 35(8), p. 2302. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000003140>.

Rana, M. and Mittal, V. (2021) 'Wearable Sensors for Real-Time Kinematics Analysis in Sports: A Review', *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 21(2), pp. 1187–1207. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3019016>.

Randell, R.K. *et al.* (2021) 'Physiological Characteristics of Female Soccer Players and Health and Performance Considerations: A Narrative Review', *Sports Medicine*, 51(7), pp. 1377–1399. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-021-01458-1>.

Rangasamy, K. *et al.* (2020) 'Deep learning in sport video analysis: a review', *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, 18(4), p. 1926. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.12928/telkomnika.v18i4.14730>.

Reed, K.E., Parry, D.A. and Sandercock, G.R.H. (2017) 'Maturational and social factors contributing to relative age effects in school sports: Data from the London Youth Games', *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 27(12), pp. 2070–2079. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.12815>.

Ribeiro, E. *et al.* (2023) 'The relative age effect in under-17, under-20, and adult elite female soccer players', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 0(0), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2022.2164608>.

Richter, A. *et al.* (2010) 'Effects Of Age, Gender And Activity Level On Counter-Movement Jump Performance And Variability In Children And Adolescents', *ISBS - Conference Proceedings Archive* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://ojs.ub.uni-konstanz.de/cpa/article/view/4438>.

Roberts, B.M., Nuckols, G. and Krieger, J.W. (2020) 'Sex Differences in Resistance Training: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*, 34(5), p. 1448. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000003521>.

Rodrigues, T.B. *et al.* (2019) 'An evaluation of a 3D multimodal marker-less motion analysis system', in *Proceedings of the 10th ACM Multimedia Systems Conference*. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery (MMSys '19), pp. 213–221. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3304109.3306236>.

Rogol, A.D., Roemmich, J.N. and Clark, P.A. (2002) 'Growth at puberty', *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 31(6, Supplement), pp. 192–200. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1054-139X\(02\)00485-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1054-139X(02)00485-8).

Romero-Moraleda, B. *et al.* (2021) 'External and internal loads during the competitive season in professional female soccer players according to their playing position: differences between training and competition', *Research in Sports Medicine*, 29(5), pp. 449–461. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15438627.2021.1895781>.

Rüeger, E. *et al.* (2022) 'Ultrasound Imaging-Based Methods for Assessing Biological Maturity during Adolescence and Possible Application in Youth Sport: A Scoping Review', *Children*, 9(12), p. 1985. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/children9121985>.

Rum, L. *et al.* (2021) 'Wearable Sensors in Sports for Persons with Disability: A Systematic Review', *Sensors*, 21(5), p. 1858. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21051858>.

Rumpf, M.C. *et al.* (2014) 'Training Profiles and Motivation of Male and Female Youth Soccer Players', *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 9(1), pp. 207–216. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1260/1747-9541.9.1.207>.

Ryan, D. *et al.* (2018) 'Developing World-Class Soccer Players: An Example of the Academy Physical Development Program From an English Premier League Team', *Strength & Conditioning Journal*, 40(3), p. 2. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/SSC.0000000000000340>.

Saki, F. *et al.* (2022) 'The effects of gluteus medius and tibialis anterior kinesio taping on postural control, knee kinematics, and knee proprioception in female athletes with dynamic knee valgus', *Physical Therapy in Sport*, 53, pp. 84–90. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ptsp.2021.11.010>.

Sánchez-Sixto, A., Harrison, A.J. and Floría, P. (2018) 'Larger Countermovement Increases the Jump Height of Countermovement Jump', *Sports*, 6(4), p. 131. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports6040131>.

Scelles, N. (2021) 'Policy, political and economic determinants of the evolution of competitive balance in the FIFA women's football World Cups', *International Journal of Sport Policy and Politics*, 13(2), pp. 281–297. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19406940.2021.1898445>.

Schepens, B., Willems, P.A. and Cavagna, G.A. (1998) 'The mechanics of running in children', *The Journal of Physiology*, 509(Pt 3), pp. 927–940. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7793.1998.927bm.x>.

Schmitz, A. *et al.* (2015) 'The measurement of in vivo joint angles during a squat using a single camera markerless motion capture system as compared to a marker based system', *Gait & Posture*, 41(2), pp. 694–698. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2015.01.028>.

Schoonjans, F. (2022) *Bland-Altman plot*, *MedCalc*. Available at: <https://www.medcalc.org/manual/bland-altman-plot.php>.

- Schulze, E., Julian, R. and Skorski, S. (2021) 'The Accuracy of a Low-Cost GPS System during Football-Specific Movements', *Journal of Sports Science & Medicine*, 20(1), pp. 126–132. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.52082/jssm.2021.126>.
- Sehrawat, J.S. and Singh, M. (2017) 'Willems method of dental age estimation in children: A systematic review and meta-analysis', *Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine*, 52, pp. 122–129. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jflm.2017.08.017>.
- Sherar, L. *et al.* (2010) 'Adolescent Biological Maturity and Physical Activity: Biology Meets Behavior', *Pediatric exercise science*, 22, pp. 332–49. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.22.3.332>.
- Shi, L. *et al.* (2018) 'DNA methylation markers in combination with skeletal and dental ages to improve age estimation in children', *Forensic Science International: Genetics*, 33, pp. 1–9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsigen.2017.11.005>.
- Shields, K.E. and Lyerly, A.D. (2013) 'Exclusion of Pregnant Women From Industry-Sponsored Clinical Trials', *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 122(5), pp. 1077–1081. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0b013e3182a9ca67>.
- Shirtcliff, E.A., Dahl, R.E. and Pollak, S.D. (2009) 'Pubertal Development: Correspondence Between Hormonal and Physical Development', *Child Development*, 80(2), pp. 327–337. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2009.01263.x>.
- Silva, B. *et al.* (2017) 'Functional Movement Screen Scores and Physical Performance among Youth Elite Soccer Players', *Sports*, 5(1), p. 16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports5010016>.
- Sinha, S. (2019) 'Celebrating Sports Technology Awards', *IEEE Potentials*, 38(3), pp. 35–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MPOT.2019.2890918>.
- Sluis, A. van der *et al.* (2015) 'Importance of Peak Height Velocity Timing in Terms of Injuries in Talented Soccer Players', *International Journal of Sports Medicine*, 36(4), pp. 327–332. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0034-1385879>.
- Solomito, M.J., Reuman, H. and Wang, D.H. (2019) 'Sex differences in concussion: a review of brain anatomy, function, and biomechanical response to impact', *Brain Injury*, 33(2), pp. 105–110. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699052.2018.1542507>.
- Sommerfield, L.M. *et al.* (2022) 'Relationship Between Strength, Athletic Performance, and Movement Skill in Adolescent Girls', *Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research*, 36(3), pp. 674–679. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000003512>.
- Spaziani, M. *et al.* (2021) 'Hypothalamo-Pituitary axis and puberty', *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*, 520, p. 111094. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2020.111094>.
- Spencer, M. *et al.* (2005) 'Physiological and Metabolic Responses of Repeated-Sprint Activities', *Sports Medicine*, 35(12), pp. 1025–1044. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2165/00007256-200535120-00003>.
- Spencer, M. *et al.* (2011) 'Fitness Determinants of Repeated-Sprint Ability in Highly Trained Youth Football Players', *International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance*, 6(4), pp. 497–508. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.6.4.497>.

- Sullivan, J. *et al.* (2023) 'Methods to predict the timing and status of biological maturation in male adolescent soccer players: A narrative systematic review', *PLOS ONE*, 18(9), p. e0286768. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0286768>.
- Svensson, M., Lind, V. and Löfgren Harringe, M. (2019) 'Measurement of knee joint range of motion with a digital goniometer: A reliability study', *Physiotherapy Research International*, 24(2), p. e1765. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pri.1765>.
- Szczerbik, E. and Kalinowska, M. (2011) 'The influence of knee marker placement error on evaluation of gait kinematic parameters', *Acta of bioengineering and biomechanics / Wrocław University of Technology*, 13, pp. 43–6.
- Tabacchi, G. *et al.* (2019) 'Field-Based Tests for the Assessment of Physical Fitness in Children and Adolescents Practicing Sport: A Systematic Review within the ESA Program', *Sustainability*, 11(24), p. 7187. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11247187>.
- Tabakin, D. (2000) 'A comparison of 3D gait models based on the Helen Hayes hospital marker set', p. 126.
- Taborri, J. *et al.* (2020) 'Sport Biomechanics Applications Using Inertial, Force, and EMG Sensors: A Literature Overview', *Applied Bionics and Biomechanics*, 2020, p. e2041549. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/2041549>.
- Tanner, J.M. (1962) *Growth at adolescence, 2nd ed.* Thomas: Springfield, Ill. (Growth at adolescence, 2nd ed).
- Taylor, J.M. *et al.* (2013) 'Within-Season Variation of Fitness in Elite Youth Female Soccer Players', *Journal of Athletic Enhancement* [Preprint].
- Thapa, R.K. *et al.* (2024) 'The effects of single and combined jump exercises utilizing fast and slow stretch-shortening cycle on physical fitness measures in healthy adult males: A randomized controlled trial.', *Montenegrin Journal of Sports Science and Medicine*, 13(1), pp. 65–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.26773/mjssm.240308>.
- Thron, M. *et al.* (2024) 'Assessing anaerobic speed reserve: A systematic review on the validity and reliability of methods to determine maximal aerobic speed and maximal sprinting speed in running-based sports', *PLOS ONE*, 19(1), p. e0296866. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0296866>.
- Till, K. *et al.* (2014) 'Considering maturation status and relative age in the longitudinal evaluation of junior rugby league players', *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 24(3), pp. 569–576. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.12033>.
- Till, K. and Baker, J. (2020) 'Challenges and [Possible] Solutions to Optimizing Talent Identification and Development in Sport', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00664>.
- Torres-Ronda, L. *et al.* (2022) 'Tracking Systems in Team Sports: A Narrative Review of Applications of the Data and Sport Specific Analysis', *Sports Medicine - Open*, 8(1), p. 15. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40798-022-00408-z>.

Towlson, C. *et al.* (2021) 'Maturity-associated considerations for training load, injury risk, and physical performance in youth soccer: One size does not fit all', *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 10(4), pp. 403–412. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2020.09.003>.

Towlson, C. *et al.* (2022) 'One of these things is not like the other: time to differentiate between relative age and biological maturity selection biases in soccer?', *Science and Medicine in Football*, 6(3), pp. 273–276. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24733938.2021.1946133>.

Tuyls, K. *et al.* (2021) 'Game Plan: What AI can do for Football, and What Football can do for AI', *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 71, pp. 41–88. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1613/jair.1.12505>.

Umek, A. and Kos, A. (2018) 'Wearable sensors and smart equipment for feedback in watersports', *Procedia Computer Science*, 129, pp. 496–502. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.03.030>.

Vaishampayan, N. and Deshpande, S.R. (2019) 'Awareness of Menstruation & Related Hygiene in Adolescent Girls - A Comparative Research Study', *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, 9(1), pp. 65–68.

VALD (2022) *Perform Better*. Available at: <https://performbetter.co.uk/pages/vald>.

Valente-dos-Santos, J. *et al.* (2012) 'Longitudinal Study of Repeated Sprint Performance in Youth Soccer Players of Contrasting Skeletal Maturity Status', *Journal of Sports Science & Medicine*, 11(3), pp. 371–379.

Vescovi, J. and Favero, T. (2014) 'Motion Characteristics of Women's College Soccer Matches: Female Athletes in Motion (FAIM) Study', *International journal of sports physiology and performance*, 9, pp. 405–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/IJSP.2013-0526>.

Vescovi, J.D. *et al.* (2011) 'Physical performance characteristics of high-level female soccer players 12–21 years of age', *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 21(5), pp. 670–678. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0838.2009.01081.x>.

Vescovi, J.D. and Jovanović, M. (2021) 'Sprint Mechanical Characteristics of Female Soccer Players: A Retrospective Pilot Study to Examine a Novel Approach for Correction of Timing Gate Starts', *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspor.2021.629694>.

Vicon Motion Systems Limited (2016) *Plug-in Gait Reference Guide*. Available at: <https://docs.vicon.com/display/Nexus215/Plug-in+Gait+Reference+Guide>.

Vincent, J. and Glamser, F.D. (2006) 'Gender differences in the relative age effect among US olympic development program youth soccer players', *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 24(4), pp. 405–413. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640410500244655>.

Walker, O. (2016a) *Countermovement Jump (CMJ)*, *Science for Sport*. Available at: <https://www.scienceforsport.com/countermovement-jump-cmj/>.

Walker, O. (2016b) *Maximal Aerobic Speed (MAS)*, *Science for Sport*. Available at: <https://www.scienceforsport.com/maximal-aerobic-speed-mas/>.

Warr, D.M. *et al.* (2020) 'Reliability of measurements during countermovement jump assessments: Analysis of performance across subphases', *Cogent Social Sciences*. Edited by Z. Lu, 6(1), p. 1843835. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2020.1843835>.

Warrier, V. *et al.* (2023) 'Height Assessment', in *StatPearls*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing. Available at: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK551524/>.

Webering, F., Blume, H. and Allaham, I. (2021) 'Markerless camera-based vertical jump height measurement using OpenPose', in *2021 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)*. *2021 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)*, Nashville, TN, USA: IEEE, pp. 3863–3869. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPRW53098.2021.00428>.

Wei, S. *et al.* (2021) 'Exploring the Application of Artificial Intelligence in Sports Training: A Case Study Approach', *Complexity*, 2021, p. e4658937. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/4658937>.

Westbrook, A.E. *et al.* (2020) 'Effects of maturation on knee biomechanics during cutting and landing in young female soccer players', *PLOS ONE*, 15(5), p. e0233701. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0233701>.

Willems, G. *et al.* (2001) 'Dental Age Estimation in Belgian Children: Demirjian's Technique Revisited', *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 46(4), p. 15064J. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1520/JFS15064J>.

Williams, R.L. *et al.* (1988) 'Adolescent self-assessment of sexual maturation: Effects of fatness classification and actual sexual maturation stage', *Journal of Adolescent Health Care*, 9(6), pp. 480–482. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-0070\(88\)80005-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0197-0070(88)80005-6).

Windt, J. *et al.* (2020) "'To Tech or Not to Tech?' A Critical Decision-Making Framework for Implementing Technology in Sport", *Journal of Athletic Training*, 55(9), pp. 902–910. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4085/1062-6050-0540.19>.

Witchel, S.F. and Topaloglu, A.K. (2019) 'Chapter 17 - Puberty: Gonadarche and Adrenarche', in J.F. Strauss and R.L. Barbieri (eds) *Yen and Jaffe's Reproductive Endocrinology (Eighth Edition)*. Philadelphia: Elsevier, pp. 394-446.e16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-47912-7.00017-2>.

Wren, T.A.L., Isakov, P. and Rethlefsen, S.A. (2023) 'Comparison of kinematics between Theia markerless and conventional marker-based gait analysis in clinical patients', *Gait & Posture*, 104, pp. 9–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2023.05.029>.

Wu, Y. *et al.* (2001) 'Racial differences in accuracy of self-assessment of sexual maturation among young black and white girls', *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 28(3), pp. 197–203. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1054-139X\(00\)00163-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1054-139X(00)00163-4).

Young, V. (2019) *Accuracy and Precision in Marker-based Motion Capture*. Thesis. Available at: <https://baylor-ir.tdl.org/handle/2104/10581>.

Yuliandra, R., Nugroho, R.A. and Gumantan, A. (2020) 'The Effect of Circuit Training Method on Leg Muscle Explosive Power', *ACTIVE: Journal of Physical Education, Sport, Health and Recreation*, 9(3), pp. 157–161. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15294/active.v9i3.39989>.

Zabaloy, S. *et al.* (2024) 'Estimation of maximum sprinting speed with timing gates: greater accuracy of 5-m split times compared to 10-m splits', *Sports Biomechanics*, 23(3), pp. 262–272. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14763141.2020.1838603>.

Zhang, J. *et al.* (2022) 'Relationships between Functional Movement Quality and Sprint and Jump Performance in Female Youth Soccer Athletes of Team China', *Children*, 9(9), p. 1312. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/children9091312>.

Zhang, W. (2022) 'Artificial Intelligence-Based Soccer Sports Training Function Extraction: Application of Improved Genetic Algorithm to Soccer Training Path Planning', *Journal of Sensors*, 2022, p. e8375916. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8375916>.

7.0 Appendices

7.1 Informed Consent Form for Chapter 1 Validating HumanTrak Movement Analysis System against Vicon Motion Capture System.

University of the West of Scotland Consent Form

Validity of HumanTrak Movement Analysis System against Vicon motion Analysis System for Lower Body Functional Movements.

Participant Consent Form

Please initial box

1. I (your name) confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the study entitled 'Validity of HumanTrak Movement Analysis System against Vicon Motion Analysis System for lower body functional movements' and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, without legal rights being affected.
3. I have been made aware of the potential risks involved with the research procedures, which are outlined in the participant information sheet provided.
4. I understand that any data obtained during the study may be viewed by the research team from the University of the West of Scotland or from regulatory authorities. I give permission for these individuals to have access to these records.
5. I agree to take part in the above study.

Participant Name:

Researcher Name:

Participant Signature:

Researcher Signature:

Date:

Date:

7.2 Informed Participant Assent and Parental Consent Form Aged 8-10 for Chapter 2 Tracking performance metrics over one -soccer season.

University of the West of Scotland Consent Form

Testing of Performance with Maturation Status in Young Female Football Players Over 1-Year.

Aged 8-10 years.

Player Assent Form

(To be completed by the child and their legal guardian)

Please write your name:

Child (or if unable, guardian on their behalf)/young person to circle yes or no below:

- Has somebody else explained this research to you? Yes/No
- Do you understand what this research is about? Yes/No
- Have you asked all the questions you want? Yes/No
- Have you had your questions answered in a way you understand? Yes/No
- Do you understand it is OK to stop taking part at any time? Yes/No
- Are you happy to take part? Yes/No

If you answered 'no' to any of the questions or you don't want to take part, do not sign your name.

If you want to take part, please write your name below

Child's Name

Date

The researcher who explained the research to you will need to sign too:

Researcher's Signature

Date

Parent Consent Form

I (Guardian's Name)

give my consent for my daughter to take part in the research study entitled '*Longitudinal Tracking of Profiling Variables with respect to Maturation Status in Academy Female Football Players*'. I have been made aware of the potential risks involved with the research procedures, all of which are outlined in detail in the separate participant information sheet provided. I understand that if my daughter wishes to withdraw their participation from the study then they may do so at any point.

Participant Name

Print Parental Name.....

Parental Signature

Date

Researcher Name.....

Researcher Signature

Date

7.3 Informed Participant Assent and Parental Consent Form Aged 11-15 for Chapter
2 Tracking performance metrics over one -soccer season.

University of the West of Scotland Consent Form

Tracking of Performance in Relation to Maturation Status in Academy Female Football Players Over One Year.

Aged 11-15 years.

Player Assent Form

(To be completed by the child and their legal guardian)

Please write your name:

Child/young person to circle yes or no below:

- | | |
|---|--------|
| - Has somebody else explained this research to you? | Yes/No |
| - Do you understand what this research is about? | Yes/No |
| - Have you asked all the questions you want? | Yes/No |
| - Have you had your questions answered in a way you understand? | Yes/No |
| - Do you understand it is OK to stop taking part at any time? | Yes/No |
| - Are you happy to take part? | Yes/No |

If you answered 'no' to any of the questions or you don't want to take part, do not sign your name.

If you want to take part, please write your name below

Child's Name

Date

The researcher who explained the research to you will need to sign too:

Researcher's Signature

Date

Parent Consent Form

I (Guardian's Name)

give my consent for my daughter to take part in the research study entitled '*Longitudinal Tracking of Profiling Variables with respect to Maturation Status in Academy Female Football Players*'. I have been made aware of the potential risks involved with the research procedures, all of which are outlined in detail in the separate participant information sheet provided. I understand that if my daughter wishes to withdraw their participation from the study then they may do so at any point.

Participant Name

Print Parental Name

Parental Signature

Date

Researcher Name

Researcher Signature

Date

7.4 Informed Participant Consent Form Aged 16+ for Chapter 2 Tracking performance metrics over one -soccer season.

University of the West of Scotland Consent Form

Longitudinal Tracking of Profiling Variables with respect to Maturation Status in Academy Female Football Players.

Aged 16+

Player Consent Form

I

give my consent to take part in the research study entitled '*Longitudinal Tracking of Profiling Variables with respect to Maturation Status in Academy Female Football Players*'. I have been made aware of the potential risks involved with the research procedures, all of which are outlined in detail in the separate participant information sheet provided. I understand that if I wish to withdraw my participation from the study then I may do so at any point.

Signature

Date

Researcher Name

Researcher Signature

Date

7.5 Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire

Medical Questionnaire for Physiological Testing

Before any physiological tests are carried on you, we will have to check whether you are in a satisfactory condition to undergo strenuous exercise. We would therefore like you to fill in the following questionnaire about yourself. All information will be treated as strictly confidential.

Name _____ Date of Birth ____/____/____

Specialist Sport (if any) _____ Male Female

PLEASE TICK ONE ANSWER ONLY

1. Have you ever had a heart attack, coronary revascularisation surgery or a stroke?

No Yes

2. Has your doctor ever told you that you have heart trouble or vascular disease?

No Yes

3. Has your doctor ever told you that you have a heart murmur?

No Yes

4. Do you ever suffer from pains in your chest, especially with exercise?

No Yes

5. Do you ever get pains in your calves, buttocks or at the back of your legs during exercise which are not due to soreness or stiffness?

No Yes

6. Do you ever feel faint or have spells of severe dizziness, particularly with exercise?

No Yes

7. Do you experience swelling or accumulation of fluid about the ankles?

No Yes

8. Do you ever get the feeling that your heart is suddenly beating faster, racing or skipping beats, either at rest or during exercise?

No Yes

9. Do you have chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, interstitial lung disease, or cystic fibrosis?

No Yes

10. Have you ever had an attack of shortness of breath that developed when you were not doing anything strenuous, at any time in the last 12 months?

No Yes

11. Have you ever had an attack of shortness of breath that developed after you stopped exercising, at any time in the last 12 months?

No Yes

12. Have you ever been woken at night by an attack of shortness of breath, at any time in the last 12 months?

No Yes

13. Do you have diabetes [Type I (Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM)) or Type II (non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM))]? If so, do you have trouble controlling your diabetes?

No Yes

14. Do you have any ulcerated wounds or cuts on your feet that do not seem to heal?

No Yes

15. Do you have any liver, kidney or thyroid disorders?

No Yes

16. Do you experience unusual fatigue or shortness of breath with usual activities?

No Yes

17. Is there any other physical reason or medical condition, or are you taking any medication(s) which could prevent you from undertaking an exercise program, or that you are concerned about? If so, please explain.*(see notes)

No Yes

18. Have you ever suffered from a viral infection in the last two weeks?

No Yes

*** NOTES: Some of these conditions might include a history of blood clotting, osteoporosis, bone fractures or serious musculoskeletal disorders, or if they have recently lost a weight without trying to. Other types of conditions might include psychiatric disorders, later-stage pregnancy or those with a history of health problems during pregnancy. Those people taking medication(s) for medical conditions listed may also need medical clearance.**

I have read, understood and completed this questionnaire. Any questions I had were answered to my full satisfaction. If there will be a change of status to any of the conditions above I will inform the researcher or the senior academic involved IMMEDIATELY.

NAME _____ SIGNATURE _____ DATE ____/____/____

References: (1) Sports Medicine Australia (SMA) pre-exercise screening system 2005, Australian Government, Department of Health and Ageing (2) American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) (2000). ACSM's guidelines for exercise testing and prescription (6th ed). New York, Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. (3) Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW) (2004). Heart, stroke and vascular diseases Australian facts 2004. Canberra, AIHW and National Heart Foundation of Australia. (4) National Heart Foundation (NHF) (2005). Physical

UWS Sport and Exercise Laboratories Screening Flow Chart

To be completed by test supervisor:	
<u>MUST BE SIGNED BEFORE THE SUBJECT STARTS EXERCISE</u>	
Checked by _____	Signed _____
Date ____/____/____	

7.6 Self-Report Puberal Development Scale

Additional Information: Amended Self-Reported Pubertal Development Scale

The Amended Pubertal Development Scale will be completed by participants aged 11-18 years. This protocol will be completed at every session before any testing begins.

Maturation is the process towards adult state and usually begins in females around 11 years old, however can vary as much as 4-5 years between healthy females (Garcia *et al.*, 2018). Peak Height Velocity is the point where maximum growth occurs in an adolescent and usually occurs around 12 years old in females (Hebestreit *et al.*, 2008; Malina, Ackerman and Rogol, 2016). Growth still continues after this point at a slower rate. Menarche, the first occurrence of menstruation (menstrual bleeding), usually occurs 2.6 years after maximum growth (Hebestreit *et al.*, 2008; Malina, Ackerman and Rogol, 2016; Koziel and Malina, 2018).

Introduction: The next questions are about changes that may be happening to your body. These changes normally happen to different young people at different ages. Do your best to answer carefully, if you do not understand a question or do not know the answer, just mark "I don't know." All answers will be kept strictly confidential.

Questions:

Questions:

1. Peak height velocity is the point where maximum growth occurs (the biggest growth spurt). Would you say that your growth spurt:
 1. Has not yet started
 2. Has barely started
 3. Has definitely started
 4. Seems complete
 0. I don't know
2. Body hair means hair any place other than your head, such as under your arms. Would you say that your body hair growth:
 1. Has not yet started
 2. Has barely started
 3. Has definitely started
 4. Seems complete
 0. I don't know

3. Some adolescents can experience skin changes (e.g. oily skin and spots). Do you feel changes to you skin:

1. Has not yet started
2. Has barely started
3. Has definitely started
4. Seems complete
0. I don't know

4. Do you feel your breast growth:

1. Has not yet started
2. Has barely started
3. Has definitely started
4. Seems complete
0. I don't know

5a. Have you begun to menstruate (started to have your period)?

- Yes
- No

5b. If yes, how old were you when you started to menstruate?

.....years

7.7 Chapter 3 Vicon Overhead Squat Graph Export

7.8 Chapter 3 Vicon Single-Leg Squat Graph Export

